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**BIG DATA
OCEAN**

BigDataOcean

“Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications”

D2.2 – BigDataOcean Methodology and MVP

Workpackage: WP2 – Stakeholders’ Identification, Maritime Data Value Chain
Definition and Project Methodology

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BigDataOcean Project Profile

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Partners

	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Decision Support Systems Laboratory, DSSLab <u>Co-ordinator</u>	Greece
	Exmile Solutions Limited (EXMILE)	United Kingdom
	Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn (UBONN)	Germany
	Centro de Investigação em Energia REN – State Grid, S.A. – R&D Nester (NESTER)	Portugal
	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)	Greece
	Ubitech Limited (UBITECH)	Cyprus
	Foinikas Shipping Company (FOINIKAS)	Greece
	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella (ISMB)	Italy
	Instituto de Desenvolvimento de Novas Tecnologias (UNINOVA)	Portugal
	Anonymi Naftiliaki Etaireia Kritis (ANEK)	Greece

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Executive Summary

The document at hand, entitled "D2.2: BigDataOcean Methodology and MVP", constitutes a report of the performed work and the produced results mainly of Task 2.4 "T2.4-BigDataOcean Methodology Elaboration and BigDataOcean MVP Definition". The scope of the current report can be considered twofold:

- Describe in detail the BigDataOcean Methodology, in the form of an integrated, clearly structured and meaningful workflow that will consequently guide the development of the BigDataOcean solution and ensure a common understanding on the solution's offerings among all BigDataOcean partners;
- Come up with and describe the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) for BigDataOcean, based on a collaborative approach among all consortium partners, in order to further clarify and promote what end-users expect from BigDataOcean, in order for the proposed solution to ensure market viability.

As far as the BigDataOcean methodology is concerned, fast prototyping sessions and existing tools' demonstrations offered valuable input towards the final result. The following figure provides a quick and easily digestible overview of the derived methodology.

Figure 0.1 BigDataOcean Integrated Methodology

Regarding the BigDataOcean MVP, all consortium partners were requested to vote on the BigDataOcean User Stories (deliverable D4.1 "BigDataOcean Technology Requirements and User Stories") on three axes (namely "Value", "Urgency" and "Technical Feasibility"), resulting in an MVP building on 14 User Stories.

The results of the current deliverable will be leveraged as input to the technical tasks of the project and will offer guidance towards efficiently describing, designing and developing the BigDataOcean solution. Updates to the work and results described here will be presented in deliverable D2.3 "Final BigDataOcean Methodology".

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List of Abbreviations

AIS – Automatic Identification System
API – Application Programming Interface
CSV – Comma-Separated Values
DB – Database
DoA – Description of Action
DSS – Decision Support Systems
Dx.y – Deliverable x.y
ETL – Extract, Transform and Load
EU – European Union
GUI – Graphical User Interface
ICT – Internet and Communication Technology
IPR – Intellectual Property Rights
JSON – JavaScript Object Notation
KML – Keyhole Markup Language
LOD – Linked Open Data Cloud
LOV – Linked Open Vocabularies
Ltd – Limited company

MIT – Massachusetts Institute of Technology

MVP – Minimum Viable Product

Mx – Month x

NCF – Nonparametric Covariance Function

OSM – Oil Spill Model

OWL – Web Ontology Language

PDI – Pentaho Data Integration

PSI – Public Sector Information

RDF – Resource Description Framework

SME – Small and Medium Enterprise

SQL – Structured Query Language

SSH – Social Science and Humanities

Tx.y – Task x.y

US – User Story

W3C – World Wide Web Consortium

WPx – Work Package x

XML – eXtensible Markup Language

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

The deliverable at hand (D2.2 “BigDataOcean Methodology and MVP”) focuses on two main concepts of BigDataOcean: the BigDataOcean Methodology and the BigDataOcean Minimum Viable Product (MVP). The work realised mainly corresponds to Task 2.4 “T2.4-BigDataOcean Methodology Elaboration and BigDataOcean MVP Definition”.

As far as the BigDataOcean Methodology is concerned, the whole route that results in the derived approach is described.

Both the front-office and the back-office components, that together constitute the integrated BigDataOcean methodology, are described in detail, and also visualised in the form of workflow diagrams.

Regarding the second main objective of the current deliverable (namely the BigDataOcean MVP), the consortium tries to group the most valuable and urgent end-users’ needs (that are taken into consideration through the BigDataOcean User Stories) under a single product that covers some of the most important needs of the users.

1.2 Methodology of the Task

The BigDataOcean consortium follows a clear and easily comprehensible methodology in order to come up with the projected results. The figure below provides a visualised overview, followed by a short descriptive explanation.

Figure 1.1 Task 2.4 Methodology

Towards defining the BigDataOcean methodology, a fast prototyping approach was followed, comprising of:

- Existing tools’ demonstrators, in order to be considered for prototyping and testing early ideas and concepts;
- Technical prototyping, in order to test the limitations and usability of existing tools that could be used in the final implementation;
- Product prototyping, in order to test the usefulness of the BigDataOcean solution.

The aforementioned steps offered valuable input to the two main components of the integrated BigDataOcean methodology, namely Front-office and Back-office methodologies.

Bringing together the derived methodology with the actual end-users' needs constitutes the step towards defining the BigDataOcean MVP. Taking as input the User Stories, the consortium is called to democratically vote on their Value, Urgency and Technical Feasibility, in order to come up with the set of User Stories that constitute the BigDataOcean MVP.

Finally, the schedule of the solution's releases is updated, based on the derived result.

1.3 Relation with other Tasks & WPs

Work package 2 ("Stakeholders' Identification, Maritime Data Value Chain Definition and Project Methodology") follows a two-cycle approach, providing results in two different moments of BigDataOcean. Deliverables D2.1 ("Analysis Report on Big Data Components, Tools and Methodologies") and D2.2 constitute the baseline for the technical developments to be performed in the context of the technical work packages of the project.

Except from D2.1, the deliverable at hand is closely related to deliverable D4.1 (and, consequently, to WP4 ("BigDataOcean Service requirements, User stories, APIs definition, Architecture"), as it receives the reported User Stories as a main input towards defining the BigDataOcean MVP.

The following figure provides a snapshot of the BigDataOcean GANTT chart, where the aforementioned interrelations are visualised.

Figure 1.2 Relation with other Tasks & WPs

1.4 Structure of the Document

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** provides an overall introduction of the deliverable objectives and positioning within the project;
- **Chapter 2** provides an overview of the existing tools' demonstrators, the technical prototyping and the product prototyping sessions that took place, followed by a quick sum-up;
- **Chapter 3** describes in detail the BigDataOcean methodology;
- **Chapter 4** describes the process towards defining the BigDataOcean MVP, as well as the derived result;
- **Chapter 5** reports summary and conclusions.

Two Annexes are also included presenting the references of the present deliverable and the aggregated results that came up from the voting process of the user stories.

2 Fast Prototyping Sessions

This chapter documents any actions taken by the partners of the consortium, either individually or collaboratively, in order to test various hypotheses concerning the BigDataOcean vision. In this context, both technical experiments were implemented to test any technical challenges that BigDataOcean will have to face during the next months of the project's duration, as well as business prototyping aiming at experimenting with new business ideas and concepts in a risk-free environment, building on the initial, general goal and vision of BigDataOcean. Additionally, any already existing solutions/tools relevant to the BigDataOcean interests that partners are considering of leveraging, either as a whole or partly, are briefly demonstrated in a dedicated subsection. Conclusions on both technical and business prototyping arose, that served as key take-aways and useful guidance for the platform's methodology and workflow creation (Section 3).

2.1 Towards Setting the high-level goal of the project – Y1

In order for the prototyping sessions to start and produce meaningful results, the high-level goal of the project should have been agreed among all consortium members, followed by key questions that the platform's methodology will have to answer.

In that view, this section starts with the definition of the high-level goal of the project - as this was initialised on the DoA and was intensely refined during this first six months of the project in multiple iterations of discussion with all partners. In support of that, the prototyping sessions that took place during this period and are being documented in the context of this chapter are serving exactly this purpose, namely to help the consortium in reaching a common agreement about what is going to be implemented in the course of the project and towards attaining which goal.

At this point, it would be useful to disconnect prototype from MVP, since these two terms are frequently confused and considered by mistake as the same. In that view, Figure 2.1 highlights these differences between the MVP, mentioned in the DoA and defined in section 4 of the present deliverable, and a prototype, which is carried out in this chapter, from two different perspectives, the technical and the business one. As the figure demonstrates, a prototype is a primitive model that aims at testing an initial idea and extract useful conclusions that may serve as knowledge to be used during product development. MVP, on the contrary, is an actual version of the product, having just the core features that allow the product to be functional and the customers to be able to appreciate its offering.

Therefore, this chapter's objective is to make the necessary actions towards identifying the main obstacles for Big Data in the maritime industry, as well as to understand what types of Big Data can maximise usefulness for maritime applications and find their common points that may accommodate the BigDataOcean vision. To make this possible, existing tool and mockups were used to test early ideas and concepts and come up with informed conclusions.

Figure 2.1 Differences between Prototype and MVP

Finally, the prototyping sessions that ran during this period allowed jointly for the partners to agree and encapsulate the high-level goal of the project under the phrase “Easily consume maritime big data”, while a number of key questions arose, and are being documented in section 2.4 as part of the product prototyping session, that should be answered towards setting this identified high-level goal. They include, among other things, questions such as whether corporations will be willing to share their business data, who will be responsible for curating the data, how will the value of the datasets will be measured, etc.

2.2 Existing tools’ demonstrators

Following the definition of the high-level goal for the project, existing tools that the BigDataOcean partners are currently possessing or handling should be identified and demonstrated in order to be considered for prototyping and testing early ideas and concepts. Eventually, the integration into the BigDataOcean solution of either the tools as a whole or reusable components of them will be examined. Along the following lines, the value, reusability, technical and IPR limitations of each of these tools are being documented, in order to provide an as clear as possible view of their functionalities and the possibility to be used for BigDataOcean.

2.2.1 LinDa

LinDA is an open-source (MIT licence¹) package of Linked Data tools for enterprises to easily consume and publish data in the Linked Data Format, interlink them with other data, analyse them and create data visualisations. LinDA as a solution consists of several independent, interconnected tools:

- LinDA Transformation Engine allows users to publish their relational data as linked data in a few, simple steps through a visual editor that enables users to inspect, match, annotate and interlink their data, possibly combining them with data from other providers or open data.
- LinDA Query Designer can be used to create simple or complex linked data queries in a drag-and-drop manner, similar to SQL Query Designers of relational database management systems. With the Query Designer one can create complex queries, join multiple data sources and apply advanced filters through an intuitive user interface.

¹ <https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT>

- LinDA Visualisation Engine can help enterprise users gain insight from the linked data that the company generates by visualising data in linked data format taking into advantage data semantics.
- LinDA Analytics enables the execution of conventional analytic processes against linked data, by integrating various Weka and R analytic algorithms such as J48, M5P, Apriori, LinearRegression, Arima, Morans I, Kriging, NCF correlogram, ClustersNumber, *Kmeans, Ward Hierarchical Agglomerative and Model Based Clustering.
- LinDA Vocabulary Repository contains an online browser and an API for storing and accessing popular and standardised Linked Data Vocabularies. The repository synchronises with well-established vocabulary catalogues (LOV, prefix.cc, LODStats) and allows enrichment with comments and rating from users, making the semantification of relational data possible.

The LinDA Workbench is an integrated offering of all of the LinDA tools that can be used either as a service or through a local installation on enterprise infrastructure. LinDA is an innovative solution that resolves typical problems identified in other linked data tools such as difficult user interfaces, various format incompatibilities and lack of end-user oriented approach.

Figure 2.2: The LinDA Workbench Concept

The purpose of LinDA is to enable enterprises to lower the learning curve of semantic technologies and harvest the potential of Linked Data in an intuitive and cost-effective manner. With the help of LinDA, SMEs can combine their corporate data with linked data from open data sources, significantly enriching the company's knowledge database in a cost-effective manner.

Several LinDA outcomes and innovations can be heavily exploited by BigDataOcean:

- Semantic web vocabularies as well as best practices in Linked Data Vocabulary management can become the basis for semantic enrichment of data in BigDataOcean.
- BigDataOcean can build upon the LinDA Query Designer & Visualisations as a basis for data exploration and visualisation, focusing on scaling these tools to be able to operate on top of big data instead of developing a similar toolset from scratch.
- Ideas from LinDA Analytics, and especially the techniques used to allow end users easily run complex analytic algorithms on heterogeneous data, can be explored on the way to BigDataOcean Analytics and Service Composition.

2.2.2 Engage

The **ENGAGE** project focuses in the development and use of a data infrastructure, incorporating distributed and diverse public sector information (PSI) resources, capable of supporting scientific collaboration and research, particularly for the Social Science and Humanities (SSH) scientific communities, while also empowering the deployment of open governmental data towards citizens. The ENGAGE e-infrastructure is envisaged to promote a highly synergetic approach to governance research, by providing the ground for experimentation to actors from both ICT and non-ICT related disciplines and scientific communities, as well as by ensuring that the scientific outcomes are made accessible to the citizens, so that they can monitor public service delivery and influence the decision making process. Simply put, ENGAGE is a door for researchers that leads them to the world of Open Government Data. By using the ENGAGE platform (open-source²), researchers and citizens will be able to submit, acquire, search and visualise diverse, distributed and derived Public sector datasets from all the countries of the European Union. With integration of over 52,000 different open datasets from multiple sources means that ENGAGE is one of the richest open data repositories at a European Union level.

The screenshot displays the ENGAGE platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the ENGAGE logo, a user profile 'dipapaspyros', and a language dropdown set to 'English'. The main navigation menu includes links for HOME, DATASETS, REQUEST DATA, COMMUNITY, OPEN DATA SITES, WIKI, and ABOUT US. The main content area shows a dataset page for '2012 Annual Statistics for Vehicular Parks in Pra'. The dataset is uploaded by 'engagecloudharvester' and has a score of 4.00 from 14 votes. It is described as 'Annuario Statistico 2012'. The page features a 'Resources' tab with a 'Detailed Metadata' sub-tab, a 'download' button, and a 'Copy url for OpenRefine' option. A 'Basic Information' sidebar on the right lists details such as Maintainer (engagecloudharvester), Publisher (dati.gov.it), Original url (Original Dataset page), Author (None specified), Release Date (March 6, 2014, 11:07 a.m.), Last Update (June 13, 2017, 9:58 a.m.), Country (Italy), Licence (Creative Commons Attribution Non-Derivatives), and Downloads (51). There is also a 'Follow dataset' button and a 'Share this dataset' section with social media icons for Twitter, Pinterest, LinkedIn, and Facebook. A vertical 'Feedback' button is visible on the right edge of the sidebar.

Figure 2.3: An example dataset in the ENGAGE Platform

ENGAGE heavily depends on community support in order to refine, enrich, update and extend existing datasets. The research community also has an opportunity drive the open data community through data requests in a way that other stakeholders can identify research needs for open data.

ENGAGE has important components that with relatively small updates could be used in the context of BigDataOcean. Dataset management as well as social features on datasets can become the basis of Dataset management, at least at an organisational and processes level, since technologically needs in

² <https://github.com/epu-ntua/opencolibri/blob/master/license.txt>

the world of big data vastly differ from those in public open data. Social interaction between the data scientists' community, authorities and other data providers is also extremely relevant with BigDataOcean, as ENGAGE concepts like Dataset Requests can work as an example for similar BigDataOcean workflows. Finally, extended use of infographics in ENGAGE was a key to its success and community growth, as it allowed for easy communication of complex data, showing that the practice of using infographics to convey information can be more powerful than other, more traditional data visualisation forms.

2.2.3 MarineTraffic

Exmle Solutions Ltd operates MarineTraffic, the world's leading platform offering vessel tracking services and actionable maritime intelligence. MarineTraffic is an end-to-end service that tracks vessel positions, based mainly on the Automatic Identification System (AIS), and displays them on the map at real-time. The AIS data is collected from MarineTraffic's own receivers network, comprising of over 2,000 coastal AIS stations around the globe, the world's largest proprietary AIS network. At any given time, MarineTraffic is tracking over 180,000 vessels at real-time with 200,000 vessels reporting daily. With its Big Data infrastructure, MarineTraffic receives hundreds of millions of vessels' positions daily and archives billions of records.

Vessel positions are gathered by dedicated load balanced servers behind virtual IP addresses, which execute the initial data filtering and add them to messaging queues governing the distribution of data to the subsequent layer of the application. A distribution service is then used to pick-up positions from the messaging queues and to send them to the central database and other relevant systems, as well as distribute them as raw data to third parties. This architecture is highly scalable both horizontally and vertically, allowing for complete separation of concerns.

All collected information is sent to MarineTraffic's central database. The central database processes the incoming data, stores the most important part of it and, finally, utilises it to display the relative information on the MarineTraffic Live Map, blended with global weather data (wind and temperature). Ports' and areas' geographic information is also stored along with other information. Thus, users of MarineTraffic can have access to any vessel's position history, statistics and details among other services or use this information to build their own applications using MarineTraffic API services. Data received is uploaded in MarineTraffic proprietary database in real time and, therefore, it is immediately available on the Live Map and on other pages. A proprietary notifications alert system, is constantly used by MarineTraffic community members that wish to keep up-to-date with all the latest occurrences regarding vessels and ports of interest.

In the BigDataOcean context a similar approach will be followed either through using the existing MarineTraffic API services³ or through using new "microservice"-style components developed for the project needs. Microservices are scalable software development methods that are considered ideal for supporting wide range of platforms and devices. Microservice architecture uses component services to build a microservice and is driven by business capabilities, focusing on products instead of projects. It relies on distributed techniques for data management with decentralised governance, while it is designed to be fault tolerant and work efficiently with real-time data. Such services are expected to

³ <https://www.marinetraffic.com/en/ais-api-services>

promote the project's adaptability and allow the core service engine to serve multiple clients in different business scenarios.

The terms of use for MarineTraffic⁴ have to be respected from any external to the platform stakeholder.

2.2.4 Oil Spill Model / Poseidon

POSEIDON OSM is the oil spill model operationally used by the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR) in the Aegean and Ionian Seas to provide oil spill dispersion simulations using the atmospheric, oceanographic and sea state forecasting results that are produced during the daily operation of POSEIDON System. It is a 3-D Lagrangian, numerical model that simulates the pollutant transport (physical movement of the oil in the marine environment) and weathering (transformation of the oil due to interaction with the sea and atmosphere: evaporation, emulsification, sedimentation, beaching), while the oil slick is represented as "parcels" with time dependent chemical and physical characteristics.

In the current operational implementation of POSEIDON OSM, the model uses atmospheric data from the POSEIDON ETA weather forecasting system, wave data from the POSEIDON WAM Cycle 4 for Aegean and oceanographic data from the POSEIDON Aegean model based on POM. The forecast length extends from few hours up to availability of the required forcing data (typically 5 days).

Figure 2.4 The Oil Spill Model's offering

The required input information consists of data that specify the event and the oil spill:

- location of the event (Lat/Lon),
- date and time of the event,
- total volume of the oil released into the sea,
- number of particles describing the volume,
- critical density for evaporation and emulsification,
- retention time (how long an oil particle stays in the beach),

⁴ <https://www.marinetraffic.com/en/p/terms>

- evacuation time (instant disposal in the sea or not),
- total time of model integration.

Bathymetric data are also introduced into the model, while the required meteorological and oceanographic data include the wind speed/direction and the air temperature from the atmospheric forcing, the significant wave height/ direction and the wave period from the wave data, the temperature, salinity and flow field for the whole water column together with the advection terms and the vertical mixing coefficients from the hydrodynamic data.

The OSM model is developed using the FORTRAN programming language and is able to handle NetCDF environmental input files that they follow certain specifications, along with an ASCII file with the necessary oil spill information.

The predicted output variables of the model contain the position of each particle in the sea (longitude, latitude and depth), the evaporated volume of the initial oil, the emulsificated volume, the volume remain in the beach and the oil volume reached the sea floor. The output is derived in an ASCII file format and it can be plotted using MATLAB routines.

The model can be triggered through a web based user-friendly interface⁵ and can be used either in forecasting mode for the next five days or in hindcasting mode using the archived data of last month. The user can submit into the system his/her own oil spill simulation scenario by providing all the required parameters and receives the results in less than fifteen minutes. The final output consists of a series of sequential graphs showing the oil spill dispersion for the requested time period that can be downloaded in zip file together with the full model output file. There is also the possibility for the user to receive the results in Google Earth KML format for a more realistic geospatial representation.

Figure 2.5 Explanatory screenshots for the use of Oil Spill Model

⁵ <http://osm.hcmr.gr>

The service is addressed to marine related authorities, organisations, entities or companies as well as to research centres and universities. The access is restricted to registered users only.

In the BigDataOcean context the requests and results will be handled by the BigDataOcean platform and the model execution will be handled by HCMR. The user will make a request in the BigDataOcean platform providing as many information as possible for the oil spill event. The input data together with the forecasting data and all the other relevant data available in the BigDataOcean database will be pushed to POSEIDON OSM through an API call. The results (in JSON or NetCDF format) will be sent back to the BigDataOcean platform and will be available to the user in download and view mode.

The POSEIDON OSM is provided under a proprietary licence.

2.2.5 Ontario

Ontario is an open source (MIT licence) data management tool that can be used to support the Big Maritime Data sources harmonisation. Ontario relies on a Data Lake to store both streamed data generated by sensors, as well as historic, social, scientific, biological, and open data. In the Data Lake, data is ingested in raw formats, e.g., CSV, JSON, or RDF, and is accessed using native data management engines, e.g., SQL or NoSQL engines. Ontario builds a Semantic Layer on top of this Data Lake, which is responsible for mapping data into existing Semantic vocabularies/ontologies, as well as querying these data in their native query languages. Ontario Semantic Layer allows users to deal with heterogeneous data as if it was in one unique format. Furthermore, Ontario implements data processing techniques that enables query processing and data analytics over data collected from heterogeneous data sources.

During data processing, data is extracted, queried, and analysed using a unique high-level declarative query language, e.g., SPARQL or SQL. In order to provide a unified query processing layer, Ontario implements the following three steps:

1. **Query analysis and decomposition:** The query is decomposed into sub-queries. An execution plan is generated. Ontario query decomposition and planning techniques are tuned to identify query execution plans that minimise execution time.
2. **Selection of relevant data sources:** Relevant datasets are selected starting from the generated sub-queries and using the mappings between the data sources and global ontology, i.e., rules that map data sources and the ontologies and vocabularies under investigation.
3. **Extraction of the results:** The sub-queries are translated into queries against the native engines of the selected sources. These queries are executed and answers are merged to produce the query answer.

The main characteristics of Ontario are that the query execution process does not require any data materialisation or shipping, and is fully transparent to the user. Data extraction rather happens fully on-the-fly upon queries are posed on the Ontario query interface.

Data Model. Data in Ontario is conceptually modelled around RDF classes. Each class can be seen as a star-shaped graph centred on the RDF subjects of the same type. The properties of a class consist of all the predicates found connected to that class, even if they were dispersed across different data sources. Thus, the data in the Semantic Data Lake is conceptually represented as a set of class instances. Thanks to the Semantic Mappings associated with each dataset in the lake, every data instance has a class, even if it is not RDF.

Architecture. Ontario extends the mediator-wrapper architecture with one extra layer in the middle. This additional layer describes data in data sources in terms of RDF classes in the global ontology, and allows for the integration of heterogeneous data around RDF classes.

- **Mediator:** Decomposes SPARQL queries into sub-queries composed of triple patterns that share all one variable in the subject position of the triple patterns. These sub-queries are commonly named star-shaped groups. Once query decomposition is performed, meta-wrappers that will evaluate the star-shaped groups are identified. Next, Ontario query optimiser identifies a bushy tree plan evaluating the star-shaped sub-queries in the selected meta-wrappers, i.e., a balanced binary tree plan where star-shaped groups correspond to the leaves.
- **Meta-Wrapper:** Each star-shaped group is submitted to a Meta-Wrapper which evaluates the star-shaped group by contacting the relevant wrappers. Meta-wrappers are also able to merge answers produced by the wrappers, and produce thus, the answers for the submitted subquery.
- **Wrapper:** The Wrappers are components able to translate conjunctions of triple patterns into a query against the final data source, as well as convert answers produced by the sources into the format understood by the corresponding meta-wrapper. Wrappers are selected by the Meta-Wrappers to collect data from the sources that is relevant for answering the sub-query posed against a meta-wrapper.

Figure 2.6: The Ontario Data Lake Architecture

Example. A demonstration of the functionality of Ontario for an exemplary SPARQL query running over Ontario, aiming to retrieve "Which tanker vessels have arrived at the port of Piraeus this month" is presented below; Figure 2.5 presents this query. It is assumed that two heterogeneous datasets need to be queried, namely a csv file with the names of all vessels along with their types and an RDF file with the arrivals of all vessels at the Greek ports. The Mediator will decompose the SPARQL query into star-shaped groups and will generate a corresponding execution plan, as shown in Figure 2.6. Each star-shaped group will be submitted to a Meta-Wrapper which will select the relevant wrapper(s) based on pre-defined mappings. Using those mappings, the wrapper is able to convert the star-shaped group,

sent from the Meta-Wrapper, into an executable query. For example, in Figure 2.6, the wrapper converts the star-shaped group into an SQL query. Wrappers' individual results are joined according to the execution plan generated during query planning.

Figure 2.7: Exemplary SPARQL query against Ontario

Figure 2.8: Ontario - Query Decomposition and Query Planning for an exemplary SPARQL query

The main advantages and limitations of Ontario can be summarised as follows:

Advantages

- Query heterogeneous data in their native query language
- Query disparate data from different data sources
- Semantic enrichment and integration on demand allows for the semantic description of data that is only required to answer the requested queries.

Limitations

- Mappings and corresponding wrappers have to be created per dataset
- Query translations introduce overhead

Solving interoperability across heterogeneous sources during execution time may impact on the execution time.

2.3 Technical Prototyping

This section is responsible for documenting any technical tests that took place during the first six months of the project. In contrast with the testbed reported in D2.1, where the features, IPR and installations

are being evaluated, the goal of this section is to test the limitations and usability of existing tools that could be used in the final implementation.

2.3.1 Experimenting on the data check-in process

In order to support the data check-in methodology as this is described in a following section (namely section 3.2.1), a test-bed environment was setup. The scope of the experiment was to analyse and identify the benefits and restrictions of the selected methodology. In brief, the process included the extraction of a data set stored in a relational database, the transformation of the data to semi structured data (CSV) that would be semantically annotated in the next step by the annotator/mapper so as to be further transformed to RDF triples and finally stored in a NoSQL database. This process is graphically illustrated in Figure 2.9 and it follows the methodology described in section 3.2.1 with the exception of the data cleaning process which was optional.

The first step in our process included the generation of the relational database that would be used for experimentation. In order not to use completely arbitrary raw data, a fraction of the data that were made available to the consortium by the consortium partner EXMILE was utilised.

The sample dataset that was used is provided below:

```
SHIP_ID,STATUS,STATUS_NAME,SPEED,LON,LAT,COURSE,HEADING,TIMESTAMP,LENGTH,WIDTH,FLAG_CODE,SHIPTYPE,TYPE_NAME
443351,15,Default,0,-58.34315,-34.62647,65,511,06-05-11 0:00,30,8,0,52,Tug
112529,15,Default,0,8.423387,55.47182,198,511,06-05-11 0:00,0,0,219,10,Reserved
620056,15,Default,1,5.65851,51.96186,320,511,06-05-11 0:00,31,5,230,99,Other
598505,98,Aid to Navigation,0,-3.508397,53.48074,0,0,06-05-11 0:00,10,10,232,103,OffShore Structure
59826,14,Nav Aid - SART - MOB,0,27.17805,40.68861,0,0,06-05-11 0:00,NULL,NULL,271,130,Manned VTS
1039551,15,Default,0,-122.4541,45.59897,211,511,06-05-11 0:00,38,7,101,73,Cargo - Hazard C (Minor)
634335,99,Class B,57,120.3334,26.99601,46,511,06-05-11 0:00,20,4,110,30,Fishing
104047,99,Class B,40,-90.26355,38.52704,356,511,06-05-11 0:00,70,31,118,52,Tug
9910,0,Underway using Engine,47,19.02991,47.82034,278,511,06-05-11 0:00,23,9,203,79,Cargo
```

This dataset was multiplied as needed in order to reach a total of 81 million records. The number of records was arbitrary and was selected just in order to push the (relational) data check-in process to the edge of the big data domain.

Figure 2.9: Data Check-In prototype

The second step of the process included the extraction and transformation of the data found in the relational database in a semi-structure dataset (CSV). In order to extract the data in a predefined semi-structured CSV file an open source data integration tool has been used called Pentaho Data Integration (formerly known as Kettle).

Pentaho Data Integration (PDI) is the leading open source Extract, Transform and Load (ETL) tool on the market. PDI is composed of four elements which are the following:

- data extraction from source databases, supporting all well-known relational databases;
- transport of the data;
- data transformation supporting user-defined criteria;
- Loading of data into a data warehouse.

PDI also offers a set of tools and services which allows data manipulations across multiple sources along with GUI applications that allow the user to define data integration jobs and transformations.

In this process, and only for the experiment's needs, the columns "FLAG_CODE" and "TYPE_NAME" were discarded as irrelevant, just for experimentation purposes.

The cleaning process was not performed during the prototyping process, as it was considered less significant as opposed to the other processes included in the workflow.

In the third step, the semi-structured dataset was served to the Annotator (Mapper) process. The main responsibility of the Annotator is to semantically enrich the dataset based on the provided ontology and the transformation of CSV files to RDF triples. Within the context of the current prototype, we used a sample custom lightweight ontology (*vessel is a shiptype has length has width*) just to semantically enrich the information so that we could in turn transform it into RDF triples.

In order to execute the annotation process, an open source tool called Apache Jena was used. Apache Jena is an open source Java framework for building Semantic Web applications. It provides extensive Java libraries for helping developers develop code that handles RDF, RDFS, RDFa, OWL and SPARQL in line with published W3C recommendations. It contains interfaces for representing all the key concepts of RDF like models, resources, properties, literals, statements. Jena also includes a rule-based inference engine to perform reasoning based on OWL and RDFS ontologies, and a variety of storage strategies to store RDF triples in memory or on disk.

In the last step, the RDF triples produced in the previous step were stored inside a NoSQL database so as to be utilisable by the software components of the BigDataOcean platform. For this purpose, the selected storage solution is MongoDB. MongoDB is a free and open-source cross-platform document-oriented database. It is a NoSQL database that uses JSON-like documents with schemas. MongoDB is capable of maintaining large amount of unrelated complex data sources offering the scalability, high availability and flexibility along with powerful querying and indexing capability needed in Big Data solutions.

Within the context of the data check in prototype in BigDataOcean, the 81 million triples generated were stored in a Mongo DB v.3.4 setup and hosted in the premises of UBITECH. The check-in process lasted approximately 4 hours (3 hours and 52 minutes) and the storage required equalled to 16,75 GB, as opposed to the 7,8 GB required for the storage of the raw information in MySQL.

2.3.2 Technical Experiments for selecting storage solution

One of the core technical requirements of BigDataOcean is the effective storage of the various datasets in the platform, as it will have significant influence on the required storage size by the infrastructure and the resulted performance, in terms of speed and effectiveness, for the querying and data accessing operations. Therefore, the selection of the most suitable solution that is going to be utilised is one of the most important decisions to be made by the development team. In this context, NTUA and UBITECH conducted a first round of a technical experiment for benchmarking the performance of both traditional and NoSQL databases during the execution of some common data import and querying operations, which is described as follows.

2.3.2.1 First Experiment's set up

A testbed environment was set up in order to compare the performance of PostgreSQL as the relational storage solution and MongoDB as the NoSQL solution. Sample datasets were generated that included values of a variable, that depended on both location and time, which is considered as representative of many datasets that are going to be available in the platform. The experiment's data that was loaded into the MongoDB consisted of JSON documents with the following structure:

```
{
  "_id" : ObjectId("592d3bd8e2160f2528287888"),
  "lat" : -9.6,
  "lng" : 12.4,
  "value" : 0.7877,
  "time" : ISODate("2016-01-01T17:00:00.000Z")
}
```

In PostgreSQL, the corresponding tables that were created, included columns for the respective properties of the JSON documents.

During the technical experiment, the size of the testing data varied from 1 thousand rows/document-table to 200 million rows/document-table and distinct cycles of the experiment were performed either using or not indices. The benchmarking operations and the measured properties included the following:

Table 2-1 Technical experiment's operations and measured properties

Operation	Measured Property
Data Import	Elapsed Time (sec) - Disk Usage (MB)
Select Query	Elapsed Time (sec)
Join Query	Elapsed Time (sec)

Assumptions

The Select Query performed a simple check on the attribute "lat" and as regards the sample dataset, 5% of the stored data were the result that was returned.

The Join Query performed an operation that discovers, between two datasets, the largest distance of the values of the variables with the same "lat", "lng" and "time". The exact queries that were performed are the following:

PostgreSQL:

```
SELECT * FROM (
  SELECT t1.lat, t1.lng, t1.time, (t2.value - t1.value) AS difv
```

```

FROM t1
JOIN t2 ON t2.lat=t1.lat AND t2.lng=t1.lng AND t2.time=t1.time
) AS Q1
ORDER BY difv

```

MongoDB:

```

db.c1.aggregate([
  {
    "$lookup":
    {
      "from": "c2",
      "localField": "lat",
      "foreignField": "lat",
      "as": "c2"
    }
  },
  {
    "$unwind": "$c2"
  },
  {
    "$project": {
      "lat": 1,
      "lng": 1,
      "time": 1,
      "isLatEqual": { "$eq" : [ "$lat", "$c2.lat" ] },
      "isLngEqual": { "$eq" : [ "$lng", "$c2.lng" ] },
      "isTimeEqual": { "$eq" : [ "$time", "$c2.time" ] },
      "diff": {'$subtract': ["$value", "$c2.value"]},
    },
  },
  {"$match": {'isLngEqual': true, 'isTimeEqual': true}},
  {"$sort": {'diff': 1}},
])

```

Results

Data Import

	Elapsed Time (sec)				Disk Usage (MB)			
	PostgreSQL	MongoDB	PostgreSQL + Index	MongoDB + Index	PostgreSQL	MongoDB	PostgreSQL + Index	MongoDB + Index
1K	0.04	0.04	0.08	0.075	0.09	0.07	0.29	0.14
10K	0.41	0.51	0.771	0.849	0.61	0.73	1.83	0.93
100K	3.91	4.02	5.78	5.7	5.78	7.30	16.75	8.90
500K	8.72	11.73	19.6	23.92	28.75	36.52	83.99	44.31
1M	20.32	36.77	41.72	48.39	57.48	73.04	166.77	89.77
5M	143.02	152.32	252.04	183.525	287.30	366.35	840.96	495.13
10M	327.47	371.86	453.732	391.828	718.27	916.00	1673.55	990.22
20M	538.61	644.87	535.344	637.54	1149.07	1656.35	2437.51	1981.56
200M	4829.66	6738.05	5795.22	7027.78	11504.28	16727.73	24374.32	19958.52

Figure 2.10: Data Import (without indices) – Elapsed Time (sec)

Figure 2.11: Data Import (with indices) – Elapsed Time (sec)

Figure 2.12: Data Import (without indices) – Disk Usage (MB)

Figure 2.13: Data Import (with indices) – Disk Usage (MB)

Select and Join Queries

	Select Elapsed Time (sec)				Join Elapsed Time (MB)			
	PostgreSQL	MongoDB	PostgreSQL + Index	MongoDB + Index	PostgreSQL	MongoDB	PostgreSQL + Index	MongoDB + Index
1K	0.03	0.01	0.017	0.003	0.02	1.59	0.02	1.19
10K	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.30	195.86	0.29	53.13
100K	0.60	0.31	0.09	0.03	7.39	-	-	-
500K	1.72	0.69	0.24	0.09	-	-	-	-
1M	2.93	1.41	0.51	0.2	-	-	-	-
5M	6.98	2.41	5.86	2.604	-	-	-	-
10M	12.72	6.25	5.43	2.817	-	-	-	-
20M	23.43	12.70	11.31	5.161	-	-	-	-
200M	405.29	229.53	65.388	29.891	-	-	-	-

Figure 2.14: Select (without indices) – Elapsed Time (sec)

Figure 2.15: Select (with indices) – Elapsed Time (sec)

Initial Results

1. The data import with batched inserts was about 10-20% faster in PostgreSQL at the most cases.
2. The disk usage of PostgreSQL was more efficient than MongoDB's without indices, but less efficient when indices were set.
3. The select queries in MongoDB were significantly faster (from 2 to 4 times faster) than in PostgreSQL.
4. The join queries were significantly faster in PostgreSQL than in MongoDB. In addition, in PostgreSQL, joins of 200,000 x 200,000 rows were succeeded, whereas in MongoDB, memory errors were raised after joins of 20,000 x 20,000 rows.

2.3.2.2 Second Experiment's set up

A second testbed environment was also set up in order to compare the performance of MySQL as the relational storage solution and MongoDB as the NoSQL solution. Sample datasets were generated that included values of a variable, that depended on time, which is considered another representative of datasets that are going to be available in the platform.

Testbed

The storage engine is the database component that is responsible for managing how data is stored, both in memory and on disk. MongoDB supports multiple storage engines, as different engines perform better for specific workloads. Choosing the appropriate storage engine per use case can significantly impact the performance of the corresponding applications.

MMAPv1 is the original MongoDB storage engine and is the default storage engine for MongoDB versions before 3.2. It performs well on workloads with high volumes of reads and writes, as well as in-place updates.

WiredTiger is the default storage engine starting in MongoDB 3.2. It is well-suited for most workloads and is recommended for new deployments. WiredTiger provides a document-level concurrency model, checkpointing, and compression, among other features.

In the proposed testbed environment both MMAPv1 and WiredTiger storage engines were tested, in order to compare data size growth as well as query execution time. The example scenario uses two collections, one to store sensor information and one to store sensor values. The experiment's data that was loaded into the MongoDB consisted of JSON documents with the following structure:

SENSOR document sample

The first collection holds documents that contain sensor name and sensor type.

```
_id: ObjectId('592d2fca86eed404f30c6c53')
type: "Temperature"
name: "Sensor 2"
```

VALUE document sample

The second collection holds documents that contain sensor name, sensor value as well as timestamp.

```
_id: ObjectId('592d362396e89a08bc36f2d1')
timestamp: 2002-04-07 18:34:55.000
sensor: "Sensor 3"
value: 89
```

Querying

The goal was to get a result set of the recent sensor values stored but also contain sensor information like type which is stored in another collection. This can be achieved with a \$lookup pipeline aggregation. \$lookup performs a left outer join to an unsharded collection in the same database to filter in documents from the "joined" collection for processing. The \$lookup stage does an equality match between a field from the input documents with a field from the documents of the "joined" collection.

To each input document, the \$lookup stage adds a new array field whose elements are the matching documents from the "joined" collection. The \$lookup stage passes these reshaped documents to the next stage.

Expected result set

```
{
  "_id" : ObjectId("592d362396e89a08bc36f2d0"),
  "timestamp" : ISODate("1990-07-18T08:44:46Z"),
  "sensor" : "Sensor 5",
  "value" : 82,
  "details" : [
    {
      "_id" : ObjectId("592d2fdb86eed404f30c6c56"),
      "type" : "CO2",
      "name" : "Sensor 5"
    }
  ]
}
```

}

Aggregation Pipeline

The following aggregation operation on the value collection joins the documents from value with the documents from the sensor collection using the fields name from the value collection and the sensor field from the sensor collection:

```
db.value.aggregate([
  {
    $lookup:
    {
      from: "sensor",
      localField: "sensor",
      foreignField: "name",
      as: "details"
    }
  }
]).pretty();
```

Indexes

Indexes support the efficient execution of queries in MongoDB. Indexes are special data structures that store a small portion of the collection's data set in an easy to traverse form. The index stores the value of a specific field or set of fields, ordered by the value of the field. The ordering of the index entries supports efficient equality matches and range-based query operations. In addition, MongoDB can return sorted results by using the ordering in the index. To enhance efficiency for the specific queries, we have also added one more index in the value collection for the key sensor.

Results

The aggregation pipeline against an incrementing number of documents was run.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1		MongoDB (No replication or sharding)					MySQL (Storage Engine: InnoDB) (No replication or clustering)		
2	Number of documents	File Size (MB) (MMAPv1)	Data Size (MB) (MMAPv1)	Data Size (MB) (WiredTiger)	Query (ms)	Left outer join (ms)	File size (MB)	Query (ms)	Left outer join (ms)
3	1,000	67	0.11	0.07	0	7	1	2	3
4	10,000	67	1.12	0.73	0	12	9	56	78
5	100,000	67	11.2	7.3	1	14	18	134	186
6	500,000	201	56	36	2	15	39	711	1285
7	1,000,000	469	112	73	2	15	64	2052	3602
8	2,000,000	1006	224	146	3	17	115	6253	9585
9	5,000,000	2080	560	365	3	19	258	26356	28492
10	10,000,000	4226	1120	730	4	19	496	-	-
11	20,000,000	6373	2240	1460	5	20	-	-	-
12									
13	50,000,000	14959		3650	7	22	-	-	-
14	60,000,000	19251		4380	7	22	-	-	-

Figure 2.16: Aggregation Pipeline Against an Incrementing Number of Documents

Figure 2.17: File Size (MB) – Number of Documents in Mongo and MySQL

It is obvious that MySQL is more efficient file size wise since significant storage space is saved compared to Mongo.

Figure 2.18: Query Time – Number of Documents in Mongo and MySQL

It is obvious that Mongo is more efficient query time wise since significant time is saved compared to MySQL.

Figure 2.19: Left Outer Join Time – Number of Documents in Mongo and MySQL

It is obvious that Mongo is more efficient left outer join time wise since significant time is saved compared to MySQL.

2.4 Product Prototyping/ A marketplace prototype for Big Data consumers

This section's objective is to document the product prototyping experiment, ran by NTUA to test with customers (i.e. in the BigDataOcean context the pilot partners) the usefulness of the BigDataOcean solution as a marketplace for Big Data consumers.

In order to define the long-term, customer-centric goal for BigDataOcean, NTUA has initiated an internal prototyping session, based on a promising and emerging prototyping methodology, called "Sprint", introduced by Google Ventures (Knapp, Zeratsky, & Kowitz, n.d.). The idea behind this novel methodology is to answer crucial questions through developing and testing a prototype in a 5-day well-structured process.

The proper, official process proposed by the book defines an organised, methodical approach for brainstorming and decision-making to select the strongest solutions. In the end, a realistic prototype is being built and, for the final step of the sprint, target customers are being recruited and interviewed to record their reactions on the prototype and the new ideas presented, thus acquiring valuable feedback even before making the expensive commitment to launch these new ideas.

As is probably expected, the limitations imposed by an EU co-funded project, with partners all around Europe, did not facilitate to "go big" since day one and include every partner in the process. Instead, a "lean" approach was adopted, scaling down the envisioned sprint session in a 2-days process, testing certain initial ideas in smaller scale and measuring the positive outcomes as well as the difficulties

imposed. It was decided that a possible prototyping session in a bigger scale will be reconsidered for the near future.

In particular, 7 people in total participated in the sprint session, being all researchers of the DSS Lab team from NTUA. The fact that all members had previous knowledge on the project, as well as that some initial work had preceded individually from each one of them, allowed the compression of time duration from 5 to 2 days, as already mentioned, while on the same time ensuring its successful completion with meaningful results. In parallel to that, the selection of the members to participate in the sprint session was made in order to ensure diversity. In this context, diversity in the team came from the different perception and background of each team member, covering both business and technical expertise.

The team did not book a full week, but in order to test the methodology one day was booked initially, and then a second day session was deemed necessary and was scheduled later taking up the baton from the first days' accomplishments.

A description of the process followed and the results produced during these two days of sprint can be found along the following lines.

Day 1

Day 1 started with the NTUA team gathering in a conference room at DSS Lab's offices in Athens.

First step, before proceeding with the process, was to define the different roles during the sprint. From the 7 team members, one had to be the "Facilitator", being responsible for the proper conduct of the procedure, whereas a "Decider" was also imposed in order to have the authority to make decisions in cases where there is conflict. Both roles were selected wisely building on the knowledge and expertise of the first on the "Sprint" book and the decision-making experience of the second, as project manager. The team had first to run into the big question: Which is BigDataOcean's long term goal? Although, the answer could seem straightforward from a first glance, a round table discussion had to be accomplished in order for all the team to be aligned. The discussion ended with the definition of the long term goal of the project as well as certain questions that emerged from the discussion and were considered key questions to be answered during the project duration, and they are as follows:

Long Term Goal: EASILY CONSUME MARITIME (BIG) DATA

Sprint Questions

1. Will corporations be willing to share their Business Data?
2. Will authorities collaborate to make available their Data?
3. Who will curate the data?
4. How will the value of the datasets be measured?
5. Will the service be fast enough to cover users' needs?
6. Will the users be able to find homogeneous data on what they look for?
7. Why users will keep coming after the 1st time (return)?
8. Will users trust us?

Afterwards, the team was ready to proceed with the design of the customer map, in compliance with the Sprint book directives. The objective of the map was to create a diagram that will showcase how customers will move through BigDataOcean's service. After a dedicated discussion among the team a first approach for the customer map was accomplished. However, a lot of iterations and modifications

had to be undertaken during the first day in order to come up with the final customer map that will best represent the project's vision and this was only possible at the very end of the day.

In order to achieve this goal, the team had to go through the "experts" session, as suggested by the "Sprint" book, by going through all the pilot cases that had been presented in the kick-off meeting and described in the Description of Action. Previous experience of all team members in the project facilitated the process that ran faster than expected and the team proceeded with the identification of the "How Might We" questions (see Figure 2.20), the identification of BigDataOcean's stakeholders and their reduction in less groups and finally the refinement of the customer map, that reached its final form and is depicted in Figure 2.21.

Figure 2.20 HMW Questions about BigDataOcean's vision

Figure 2.21 Derived Sprint's Session Customer Map

For brainstorming purposes and in accordance with the "Sprint" book directives, the team had a roundtable discussion where each one of them presented existing solutions that could serve as inspiration for the BigDataOcean solution. Due to the imposed time limitations, all team members had

worked and prepared a relative state of the Art analysis for that purposes beforehand, so valuable insights were possible in a short time (Figure 2.22).

Figure 2.22 Brainstorming on existing tools and technologies in the BigDataOcean area

After that step, the sprint session had to concentrate on a specific issue to proceed with that for the prototyping phase. The team chose the question “How will the value of the datasets be measured?” as the most important to run through the prototyping phase and the step “View Resources Preview” from the customer map to focus on (see red areas on Figure 2.21). However, previous and next steps, as illustrated in the map, were also considered highly relevant with the selected step in order to be able to create something meaningful and from that point on, the team was able to allocate who will design what, during the next phase, namely the ideation phase where different designs will emerge.

After allocating the members on different steps, it was agreed that the design round will run “offline”, before the next meeting, in order for the next meeting to start with the prototyping phase. A whole working day in the upcoming week was reserved for that 2nd day sprint session and the team left the room tired but contented about the outcomes of the first-day meeting.

Day 2

The second day started with the “Museum” session, where every solution, designed by each individual member offline, was placed on the wall, and each team member commented “silently” on the design through the use of post-its and highlighted the most promising ideas (see Figure 2.24). Afterwards, “speed critique” took place, where the “Facilitator” described what each design presented, and tried to answer the questions from the post-its. Each “Creator” came up to cover all the necessary gaps, and then the team voted on the most promising ideas (colourful stickers were used for that purposes).

The “Decider”, then, came up with the three most promising “screens” to implement on the prototyping phase. Those screens were:

- a) A preview screen for the data with multiple tabs
- b) A report-synthesis screen engaged through tables of raw data

c) A report-synthesis screen enabled by a library of code to run analysis

Although these were the three screens voted for the prototyping phase, there were many other interesting ideas and concepts that our team came up with, such as an intuitive landing page with advanced search options, or a “requesting” page, that were also deemed important and kept in mind for the next steps of BigDataOcean progress. For the prototyping needs, these ideas were taken for granted and focus was put on how data review and reporting can engage users in the platform.

Figure 2.23 Elaboration and Voting on the designs

Figure 2.24 A design voted by the Decider

Day 2 ended with the decision to implement the final storyboard and the prototypes offline and then visit the pilot users to test those ideas. Thus, that was the end of the experimenting phase of using the “Sprint” methodology on a collaborative, EU co-funded project. During the following days, detailed mock-ups were created based on the ideas emerged during this experimenting phase and these mock-ups were communicated to the pilot users in dedicated meetings to get feedback from them and come up with a final, common perception on the main BigDataOcean offering.

2.5 Summary of Prototyping Sessions

Concerning the product prototyping experiment, i.e. the prototyping session implemented by the DSS Lab-NTUA team under the directions of the Google Ventures Sprint book, it should be stressed that it

was a first “experimental” prototyping phase, aiming at testing another approach from the conventional one the team has used in working. Typically, the organisation engages its members through meetings and then individuals are being assigned with the design of the mock-ups, followed by a next iteration of meeting to discuss on them. The sprint session approach, followed now, was a first-time opportunity for NTUA’s team members to participate actively throughout the whole process, regardless of each member’s expertise. The result was new, innovative ideas that emerged and guided the mock-ups development, while it also gave the opportunity to the prototyping session members to reach a common understanding on BigDataOcean’s vision as well as to come up with a BigDataOcean prototype in two days; a process that usually takes weeks and a lot of meetings to finalise.

Of course, there were certain difficulties that arose and cannot be neglected. The first difficulty that participants of the session had to overcome had to do with the reservation of a day that all team would be available. In addition to that, the restrictions posed by the prototyping “sprint” methodology regarding the use of devices, made it even more difficult for the participants that had to make use of the breaks to catch up with the rest of their tasks, answer emails, debug projects, etc. Furthermore, due to the limitations of an EU co-funded project, it was not possible for the pilots, that should typically undertake the “experts” role in the session, to be present in the meeting, due to both time constraints as well as the fact that they are also the users of the platform that will interact with the prototype. In addition to that, reservation of a whole week to implement the proposed prototyping methodology, in full agreement with the book, was also not possible. In this view, it was necessary to make certain assumptions and differentiations from the typical process; one week was compressed in two days as already mentioned, whereas a roleplaying game among the sprint team members, going through the presentations of the pilots, enabled to break down their motives and needs and undergo successfully the “experts” session.

Concluding, it needs to be noted that although the team was initially reluctant for the potential outputs of this new approach, at the end it appreciated its usefulness while the final outcomes advocated for its advantages. In this context, the team agreed to leverage again this prototyping methodology in the near future for the upcoming phases of the project, whereas its proven success degraded any persistent reluctances and thus is expected to be easier to engage more people in a full-week “meeting”. Furthermore, engagement of more partners of the BigDataOcean project in such a future session is another and even greater challenge (due to multiple obstacles, e.g. operational, organisational, geographical etc.) that is expected to be really profitable for the project.

As regards the initial technical prototyping activities that took place, several useful conclusions and directions for further experimentation and testing have been produced. The prototyping of the data check-in process has created a methodology that can be used as a good starting point towards the final implementation. Especially helpful was the fact that the technical experiment was performed using a large dataset with a relational schema coming directly from a consortium partner, so as the experiment to be close enough to the actual activities that are going to take place in the upcoming stages of the project. The next steps, are going to be the further improvement of the process based on the early experimental results, the experimentation with additional datasets coming from other sources and the extension of the process, in order to handle other types of input data.

Moreover, the benchmarking activities about the selection of the most suitable storage solution, are still in an early stage. An initial set of conclusions have been pointed out, but further experimentation is planned to be performed in the near future, as the final decision is going to have significant impact

on the performance of the final platform. Some indicative subjects that have to be examined by the technical partners are the scalability of the storage solution taking into account the future volume of the stored information, the ability to handle different types of data and the methods that are used to access them, the identification of the most frequent operations that will be made, in order to optimise their performance and more. Consequently, the technical partners are going to work further on this topic, towards the implementation of the most appropriate solution, based on the needs of the project.

3 Platform Methodology

As also stated in the previous section, BigDataOcean's high-level goal is to enable effortless consumption of maritime (big) data. In order to accomplish this goal, this section takes input on the one part from D2.1, specifically the landscape analysis on big data methodologies and tools and the work implemented on the identification of stakeholders and the data value chain definition, and on the other part the results of the experiments (both technical and business ones) taken place in section 2 of this deliverable to design a methodology that will:

- define how value will be created for each BigDataOcean stakeholder group;
- describe how the challenges identified in the previous section and D2.1 will be addressed.

The platform methodology that will be described along the following lines does not intend to come up with an exhaustive analysis of the envisioned BigDataOcean concept, since this will be gradually elaborated during the project's duration, but rather to provide a **well-constructed and meaningful workflow** that will guide the development of the BigDataOcean Web platform and will ensure that alignment on BigDataOcean offerings is reached among all BigDataOcean partners.

In that view, the platform methodology is divided in two parts: the front-office methodology (section 3.1) and the back-office methodology (section 3.2), dealing respectively with the ways of engagement for the different BigDataOcean stakeholders and the technical and scientific details on how vital steps of the methodology will be implemented.

3.1 Front-office Methodology

The aim of the front-office methodology for the BigDataOcean platform is to showcase the actions considered for each identified stakeholder group when navigating through the BigDataOcean solution, to meet the project's ultimate goal, as defined in section 2.1. These workflows that will arise are expected to then pave the way for the technical requirements elicitation, under WP4.

3.1.1 Overall Platform Methodology

In the following figure (Figure 3.1) a map is depicted illustrating the actions that each identified BigDataOcean stakeholder will implement when navigating through the BigDataOcean solution, as well as the interactions that arise among the individual steps/actions and the different stakeholders.

The presented methodology builds upon the results of the product prototyping session implemented by NTUA and described in 2.4.1 section, elaborating further on the customer map derived during the 1st day of the sprint session (Figure 2.21), through multiple iterations of discussion and feedback gathering by the consortium's partners.

In this context, four stakeholders' groups are being considered for the BigDataOcean solution: **the consumer, the data provider, the service provider and the curator**, covering in groups all stakeholders identified in D2.1.

At this point, stakeholders from users of the platform need to be distinguished. Whereas the targeted users for the BigDataOcean platform are the data consumers, the methodology should address all anticipated stakeholders involved in the BigDataOcean value proposition. In that view, it can be seen that at the centre of the map the main goal for the project can be found, namely to "easily consume maritime data". This goal matches with the ultimate goal for the data consumer, as the targeted user

of the BigDataOcean solution. For the other three stakeholder groups, while not having the same individual purpose, all steps prescribed are ultimately intended towards the accomplishment of the overall goal for the project; the easy consumption of maritime data.

In order to support better understanding of the proposed workflows, it needs to be stressed that dotted arrows represent - in the form of an input-output relation - the interactions that should emerge among the actions of the different stakeholders' groups. In this context, for example, the feedback that the consumers will leave when interacting with the platform's data and services will be given as input to the Data and Service providers through Usage Analytics.

Furthermore, although, along the following lines, the workflows are described for a user that undertakes one of the four specified roles in the platform that does not mean that alterations may not arise. Such a characteristic example is that of the Data Provider that may also turn to be a Data Consumer, after the provision of his data, consuming services on his own data or combining them appropriately with other data sources found in the BigDataOcean solution.

The following sections will analyse Platform's methodology from the perspective of each identified stakeholder group, serving as a base for the platform's requirements and giving insights on the main aspects that the platform should handle and offer.

Figure 3.1 BigDataOcean Integrated Methodology

3.1.2 Engaging Data Consumers

Figure 3.2 Data Consumer's workflow diagram for the BigDataOcean platform

Figure 3.2 illustrates how a potential consumer of BigDataOcean data or services is being engaged in the platform and navigates through it in order to accomplish its goal, to consume easily and effortlessly maritime big data. According to this approach, a consumer logs/signs up or even enters as a guest in the BigDataOcean platform and as a first step he/she browses the available datasets and services or he searches for a specific dataset or service. If he finds a dataset or service he is interested in he may enter its "Smart" Preview page and get additional information regarding certain characteristics of the provided dataset or service (e.g. provider's info, data sources, quality metrics, similar datasets etc.) or even gain better insights into its power through an "Advanced Insights" page. In the case where the service/dataset in question is not yet provided, the consumer can make a request giving a description of his demanded data service, which may either be targeted at a specific data/service provider or be an open request.

When the consumer believes he has found the dataset or service he was looking for (leveraging the Resource Preview functionality of the platform), he may explore the available access options enabled for the dataset/service in question, in order to proceed with getting access to it. After that, the consumer may experience a multitude of options provided by the platform on the dataset/service obtained. These options depend on the specific dataset/service in question and may vary ranging from the opportunity to view a whole dataset, to view a report acquired from a combination of data sources, to create a report configured on the user's specific needs, to build queries and visualisations on selected data sources, to explore and interact with analytics, to leave feedback about the services/datasets he has acquired, etc. It is exactly this plethora of options, along with the previous clear-cut steps to get there, that enable eventually for the BigDataOcean user the opportunity to consume easily maritime data either this is done directly or indirectly through appropriate service provision.

3.1.2.1 Engaging Data Providers

Figure 3.3 Data provider's workflow diagram for the BigDataOcean platform

Data provider's role and action steps should be appropriately selected in order to further support and enhance the successful accomplishment of the project's goal (as indicated by the central node at Figure 3.1). In that view, the workflow that describes data provider's navigation through the BigDataOcean platform should consider in general the following high-level steps:

- a) Uploading of his data in the BigDataOcean platform;
- b) Improvement of data: This step refers to any data curation processes implemented either by the user himself through appropriate tools offered by the platform or through the support by a Curator, either at a consultative or at a practical level. During this step, quality issues are assessed, while processes such as data compression and indexing are also investigated to ensure data and service provision of high quality;
- c) Requests Preview and response on them with appropriate data provision or data transformation for their improvement/curation;
- d) Description, Setting terms & Price: Only when the previous step is successfully completed- after possibly many iterations- and the data quality is assured, the user may proceed with the provision of his data through the platform and consecutively the description of his offering, the set-up of the terms for its provision and the pricing policy that he wishes to attribute to the data;
- e) Monitoring of usage analytics: The data provider may monitor the usage of the data he has provided in the BigDataOcean platform in order to leverage the feedback gathered by the platform users, timely identify any quality issues and recognise early the need for additional data/services.

An additional dotted arrow that points at the consumer's flow indicates that after setting the terms and the pricing model for the data provision, then the data are finally at the disposal of any interested consumer. Furthermore, the opportunity for any data provider to turn into a data consumer after the provision of his data can be also stressed at this point, either by requesting services to be built on the data he has uploaded or by combining his data with other maritime data sources that are available in the platform to acquire new, previously hidden insights that are potentially introducing new business models.

3.1.3 Engaging Service Providers

Figure 3.4 Service provider's workflow diagram for the BigDataOcean platform

A service provider plays a vital role in the BigDataOcean solution since it encapsulates one of the main offerings of the platform, namely the opportunity to leverage the abundance of maritime data to offer new knowledge and business intelligence to its end users, by contributing meaningful representations on the data, such as reports, intuitive analytics, visualisations, etc.

In this context, the service provider's navigation through the platform may follow the consecutive high-level steps; the service provider may either create a new service leveraging his own data or other maritime data of the platform or update an existing service, adapted appropriately on the data or needs of another stakeholder. Both options can come as a response to a request found in the platform. The specific parameters for the service are then provided in order for the service to be fully formed and afterwards the service provider sets the terms for its use and the pricing model that the service will follow, while he also provides a description in order to set up the "preview" page to be shown to the end users of the platform -interested in becoming service consumers- to support them in their decision to proceed or not with the acquisition of the service. As was also the case for the data provider, monitoring of usage analytics is also foreseen in order to timely cope with any emerging needs and accommodate user's feedback.

In parallel to the data provider's case, the additional dotted arrow pointing at the consumer's flow indicates the fact that the service is from that point on at the disposal of service consumers.

Furthermore, as was the case for the data provider, the opportunity for the service provider to turn into a data consumer by acquiring new data sources to be leveraged for the provision of novel services also applies here.

3.1.4 Offering curation services

Figure 3.5 Curator's workflow diagram for the BigDataOcean platform

A curator's role is imposed in order to acquire appropriate data transformation of the available datasets that will ensure data of high quality as well as the opportunity to easily process them and link them with other sources. The role of curator can be undertaken either by a platform's user that will make use of the, offered by the platform, curation services or by a dedicated person engaged for that purpose. In this context, the curator entering the platform will be firstly presented with the "open" curation needs, namely the current status of the datasets related/attributed to him with regard to their quality. After selecting a specific dataset, the curator will examine its quality and rate it accordingly and will proceed afterwards with its curation conforming to the directives emerged during the previous step or provide consultation to the corresponding data provider in order for the latter to proceed with the suggested modifications.

3.2 Back-office Methodology

Back-office methodology is responsible for clarifying the way the workflows defined above will be completed from a technical perspective, namely how any technical challenges that arise from the described workflows will be solved. Towards this goal, six different technical challenges are being examined along the following lines and the ways these challenges will be addressed during the next months of the project are being described.

3.2.1 Data check-in

The data check in process, both in general as well as in the context of BigDataOcean, refers to storage of data, either storage of newly produced data or replication of data originally stored in remote data warehouses, in the big data repository/warehouse of BigDataOcean.

Nevertheless, data check-in is not a uniform procedure and depends upon the business need. Within the context of BigDataOcean, data check in does not simply refer to the replication and storage of raw data, but to a pipeline of processes to guarantee data reuse and interoperability and to increase the value that can be generated on top of this data.

Towards this end, and as graphically illustrated in Figure 3.6, the BigDataOcean consortium came up with a series of processes to clean, harmonise, enrich and store the data so as to make them re-usable by all technical components, and by both internal and external to the consortium parties.

Figure 3.6: BigDataOcean data check in methodology

The back-office methodology of the data check-in process in the context of BigDataOcean begins with the extraction of tuples from the original data set. The original data set may be in the form of a structured (e.g. XML or JSON) or semi-structured (e.g. excel) document, it may comprise a streaming data source, or it may be stored in a relational database (e.g. MySQL) or in a NoSQL database (e.g. Mongo). The scope of the first step in the process is to provide a tabular view of the datasets, so that the meaningful sellable items can be identified and separated from the information that is not of direct value to the BigDataOcean stakeholders, or alternatively that needs to be kept private and not be disclosed to these stakeholders.

After the meaningful subset of information from the original dataset has been extracted, the second step of the process, which is however optional, given that the original dataset may be solid enough, as well as because the specific process is not fully automated but is in need of human mediation (namely be performed interactively with data wrangling tools), is the data cleaning or data cleansing. Data cleansing is the process of detecting and correcting (or removing) corrupt or inaccurate records from a record set, table, or database and refers to identifying incomplete, incorrect, inaccurate or irrelevant parts of the data and then replacing, modifying, or deleting the dirty or coarse data. After cleansing, a data set should be consistent with other similar data sets in the system. The inconsistencies detected or removed may have been originally caused by user entry errors, by corruption in transmission or storage, or by different data dictionary definitions of similar entities in different stores. The actual process of data cleansing may involve removing typographical errors or validating and correcting values against a known list of entities.

The third step in the BigDataOcean data check in process is the semantic annotation of the selected, and cleaned subset of the original dataset, using predefined ontologies and vocabularies, relating its concepts to well defined semantics, so as to allow computer reasoning about the dataset. When a dataset is semantically annotated, it becomes a source of information that is easy to interpret, combine and reuse by our computers. Within the context of BigDataOcean, the consortium has identified a set of upper domain-specific ontologies and core vocabularies which will be extended so that the domain specific business needs identified can be covered.

After the semantic annotation of the identified and cleaned datasets and prior to the transactional transfer of this information to the BigDataOcean data warehouse, the information will be transformed to RDF triples. RDF is a W3C recommended standard for representing data and metadata (i.e. description of data like its schema and business-meaning) which can support semantics-aware Business Intelligence. The idea of RDF is to represent everything in terms of triples, which are basically the data model of RDF which in turn has three components: 1) the Subject (S), 2) the Predicate (P), and 3) the Object (O). Expressing such triples help in defining the semantic meaning of data items and how they should be understood, which makes the semantic world a natural and expected evolvement of Business Intelligence for supporting the data scientists in understanding the data under their hands. Also, RDF and semantically-represented data are really useful for sharing the data with the community and making the data officially recognised as sharable open-data. The RDF triples produced will be later stored in a NoSQL database.

3.2.2 Service offering

In the context of BigDataOcean, cross-sectorial Big Data will be turned into value for the maritime stakeholders, through the offering of meaningful and innovative services. The core service offering of BigDataOcean will be based on the utilisation of well-proven Big Data Analytics frameworks in combination with the implementation of domain-specific algorithms directly within the platform. These services will constitute the core functionality of the platform. An initial set of such services is going to be developed by the technical partners in close connection with the pilot partners, in order to effectively demonstrate the benefits obtained by the proposed solution. A prime methodology for the suggested process is illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 3.7: BigDataOcean service offering methodology

The initial request of a service triggers the creation of a corresponding service instance. This instance encapsulates the required algorithms and analytical processes in order to provide the desired results. The data that are necessary for the execution of the analysis are requested by the Query Engine, which is responsible for accessing and querying the Mongo database and providing the results to the service instance.

After obtaining the data and performing any initial configuration, the data analysis and machine learning algorithms will be implemented by utilising the framework provided by Apache Spark. Apache Spark is a fast and general engine for large-scale data processing, offering an application programming interface (API) for many programming languages (Java, Python, Scala, and R) and it is recognised as the most suitable Big Data tool to be used for the platform's analytical services, especially its machine learning library (MLib), which offers a algorithms about classification, regression, correlation and more.

The service instance will be responsible for sending the appropriate Spark jobs (the analysis that need to be executed using the Spark framework) to the Cluster Manager, which is a software component that monitors and manages the resources of the computer cluster that is responsible for. Then, the Cluster Manager will undertake the responsibility for effectively distributing the analysis tasks to the nodes of the Spark Cluster (the computer cluster that runs Spark), taking advantage of Spark's functionalities.

Once the analytical process is completed, the results are sent back to the service instance. The final step of the procedure is to provide the output to the user who made the request. The output will be provided in the most comprehensive way, through meaningful visualisations, reports and other representations.

3.2.3 Interactive Service Building

One of the features that is going to be offered by BigDataOcean is the capability of interactively creating some basic analytical services using some predefined components. These components will represent useful algorithms or visualisations that can be used together as building blocks for building customised services. A simple and user-friendly interface will assist the user select the datasets that he desires to use and the specific features to be provided as input for the analytical components. The algorithms to be used will be selected from a given collection and the required parameters will be configured by the user. The connection between the components will be made by dragging and dropping them into the service building area and the platform will decide and inform the user if the connected components are eligible to be connected. The described functionality is presented in the following figure.

Figure 3.8: Interactive Service Building

The interactive service building procedure will start by selecting an initial analytical component and the dataset(s) to be provided as input. The data input will come from the stored datasets of the platform and their specific fields that will be used for the analysis. The selection of the analytical component will be followed by the definition of the required parameters so as to customise the process. The goal is that not only one, but multiple analytical components will be used, creating a chain of different actions on the data. In order to achieve this, a detailed description of the expected input and output of each component is required. An initial implementation plan of this is based on the utilisation of the Spark's ML Pipeline concept, which is a uniform set of high-level APIs built on top of DataFrames that help users create and tune practical machine learning pipelines. In this context, each pipeline component is either a Transformer or an Estimator. A Transformer is an algorithm that transforms DataFrames into other DataFrames and an Estimator is an algorithm that can be fit on a DataFrame so as to create a model that can act as a Transformer. The output of the procedure will either be meaningful reports and visualisations to the user or a model that can be used for future analysis as a service.

3.2.4 Big Data semantic annotation

Big Data Semantic Annotation is important in order to enrich existing semi-structured/unstructured data sources with additional relevant semantic information. This process, also called semantic enrichment, is executed in conjunction with data extraction and integration processes. Enriching or annotating

datasets can range from extracting new facts from unstructured sources, such as text, to inferring implicit facts from RDF data and indexing and equipping datasets with linguistic resources.

The very nature of the maritime data imposes challenges in the tasks of semantic annotations that need to be achieved in order to ensure both efficiency and effectiveness.

Volume: Existing maritime data sources provide enormous quantity of data, which cannot always be semantically enriched. Thus, semantic annotation tools need to be able to select the relevant data to be semantically enriched without considerably increasing the volume of the original data source.

Velocity: Maritime data is collected continuously from different type of sensors, e.g., to observe real-time about meteorological and oceanographic, or to determine a vessel's live conditions. Semantic enrichment processes need to incrementally annotate incoming streams of data with blocking the data flow.

Variety: Maritime data is collected in a wide variety of ways and stored in many different formats and data structures. Semantic annotation techniques should be able to semantically enrich the input datasets independently of data representations.

Veracity: Marine data is collected following a wide variety of methods and using disparate instruments; in consequence, different degrees of accuracy and uncertainty can be observed in maritime data sources. Processes of data extraction and integration, as well as semantic annotation need to be able to identify quality issues in the data, thus preventing the generation of poor-quality annotated data.

Value: Big maritime data can be utilised and exploited to enhance the value of diverse maritime data-driven applications. Semantic enrichment methods must empower the value of Big maritime data and allow for the development of applications able to exploit the semantic information encoded in the annotations.

3.2.5 Curation in maritime data

Marine measurement precision has been increased in modern devices. However, because data is collected following a wide variety of methods and using disparate instruments, different degrees of accuracy and uncertainty can be observed in maritime data sources. For example, untrained sailors may utilise poorly-calibrated and low-resolution instruments on board ships, or oceanographic buoy measurements may be impacted by buoy size, shape, ballast, and mooring. Thus, missing or inconsistent observations may be reported, and ambiguities may be present across maritime data sources. Additionally, the very nature of the maritime data imposes challenges in the task of data curation that need to be addressed in order to ensure not only good performance, but also accuracy of the results. In consequence, novel curation methods like deduplication, disambiguation, and domain specific data cleaning process must be customised for Big maritime data.

Volume: Existing maritime data sources provide enormous quantity of data, and data curation techniques need to be able to uncover patterns that represent the quality issues without the need to explore the whole set of data.

Velocity: Maritime data is collected continuously from different type of sensors, e.g., to observe real-time about meteorological and oceanographic, or to determine vessel live conditions. Big maritime data curation techniques need to be incrementally performed without blocking or delaying the streams of data.

Variety: Maritime data is collected in a wide variety of ways and stored in many different formats and data structures. Big maritime data curation techniques should be suitable for any type of data representation.

Veracity: Marine data is collected following a wide variety of methods and using disparate instruments. Data curation techniques should attempt to solve a wide range of quality.

Value: Big maritime data can be utilised and exploited to enhance the value of diverse maritime data-driven applications. Data curation techniques must empower the value of the Big maritime data by reducing quality issues and ambiguities.

3.2.6 Dataset recommendation

Given the target of collecting a large number of maritime datasets into the BigDataOcean platform, an effective dataset recommender system will be important so to ensure that each user is going to reach these datasets that will be more useful and suitable for his specific needs.

Since it is recognised that the platform will especially focus on the datasets and its contents, the most suitable approach to be followed will be the development of a recommender system of content-based filtering. This approach will produce dataset recommendations based on the included content, taking into account a profile of each user's preferences.

In order to describe the content of each dataset of the platform, a profile will be created, containing a set of discrete keywords, attributes and features, which will characterise the dataset. Many possible attributes can be included. Some indicative examples are the geographical area, the type of the data, the existing rating from the other users, other datasets that it is often combined with and more. Given the profile of each dataset, the system will try to recommend others that are similar to those that the user used in the past, gave a high rating, or is examining in the present. So the system has to be able to learn the user preferences from his actions and use them to recognise the best-matching results.

4 MVP Definition

As also stated earlier in the document at hand, an MVP is an actual version of a product, having just the core features that allow the product to be functional and the customers to be able to appreciate its offering. The BigDataOcean MVP will be used to derive the technical requirements and the architecture that will be part of deliverable D4.2 "BigDataOcean Platform Architecture, Components Design and APIs - v1.00", which will consequently lead into the development of the prototype and the initial functional versions of the BigDataOcean platform that will take place in WP5.

The realisation of a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) for BigDataOcean (stated as Most Valuable Product in the DoA) was decided in order to improve the value generated by the platform. In this context, an MVP is a product which is used in order to move fast towards the prototyping phase, without investing effort to features and operations which could hinder the overall development due to design that increases complexity without offering anything more in user acceptance or decisions that are not reversible. The MVP is directly linked with the lean start-up approach (Ries, 2011) in design and development, which is something that is fully in alignment with the concept that BigDataOcean adopts.

However, it needs to be stressed that the fact that MVP defines the minimum set of features that are necessary for a product to be deployed and validated, this does not mean that the resulting product should not be viable and profitable. On the contrary, MVP is a strategy for cutting out unnecessary spending, while on the same time being able to quickly learn from the customers in order to gradually improve the product and populate it with additional features. Towards this end, the generation of an initial MVP is essential for the smooth deployment and implementation of the project. As such, an incremental MVP methodology will be presented in the following section, which will set milestones for the platform's released, while it will continuously test the outputs against the customer's reception.

4.1 Methodology for MVP Definition

The present section defines the methodology to be followed in order to come up with the user stories prioritisation and select features that are developed and mounted first, always keeping into consideration that the support of certain activities/features is mandatory for the implementation of others.

The user stories of the platform have been defined in D4.1 that was due in M5. In order to be able to construct the MVP, two rounds of user stories voting were implemented based on a simple prioritisation model.

Following this model, the **first round** of user stories voting was based on an approach proposed by Lant⁶ which calculated a score for every user story, against two different attributes, that of value and urgency. According to this approach, business value is being calculated, in a qualitative manner using a scale between 1-5 points, by asking questions such as: 1) how important is this feature for the overall process, 2) how many users will use it and 3) how often will it be used. In the same context, the

⁶ Michael Lant (2010). How to Easily Prioritize Your Agile Stories. Available at: <http://michaellant.com/2010/05/21/how-toeasily-prioritize-your-agile-stories/>

urgency for the development of each user story is being calculated through voting, using again a list between 1-5.

The following table by Lant demonstrates the potential values regarding business value and urgency of a user story.

Table 4-1 User stories for code quality reviewing, business value/urgency dimension

Value/ Urgency	Value Guidelines	Urgency Guidelines
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extremely Important to most or all customers Extreme impact on brand or reputation Critical to the success of the business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extremely time constrained. Extreme level of dependency of other items on the completion of this task If not completed immediately there is little or no value to doing it.
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Important to many customers Significant impact on brand or reputation Significant competitive advantage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highly time constrained High level of dependency of other items on the completion of this task Important to go into the next sprint because of customer or contractual requirements
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Important to a moderate number of customers Moderate significant impact on brand or reputation Moderate important competitive advantage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderately time constrained Moderate dependency of other items on the completion of this task Desirable to complete in the next one or two sprints
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Important to only few customers Minor impact on brand or reputation Minor competitive advantage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimally time constrained Minimal dependency of other items on the completion of this task Completion in the next two or three sprints is adequate
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Important to only a few or even no customers Little or no impact on brand or reputation Little or no competitive advantage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not time constrained No dependencies Little or no impact

After collecting all partners votes, user stories can be ranked and the one that should be included in the MVP are becoming more evident. Specifically, the multiplication of the Business Value with the Urgency provides a "Priority" indicator which ranges between 1 and 25 and the higher this number is, the sooner a user story should be forwarded for implementation. Figure 4.1 clarifies further this concept.

In this first round of voting, all partners were responsible for voting on the user stories and a single vote per partner was requested. However, for the pilot partners, i.e. ANEK, FOINIKAS, HCMR, NESTER, EXMILE, their vote counted as double, in order to be given increased weight on the ones who are going to be the end users of the platform.

Figure 4.1 Priority as a multiplication between urgency & business value and explanation of the priority numbers

Afterwards, a 2nd round of voting followed, voting the user stories based on their technical feasibility, in the sense that even if a user story has been rated high during the 1st round of voting and is being considered of high priority, it might not be feasible from a technical perspective in a short time frame or it might be connected with other activities/features which are calling for more time to be implemented.

In that view, only the technical partners, i.e. UBONN, NTUA, UBITECH, EXMILE, where requested to vote in this 2nd iteration, in order to assess the technical feasibility of the user stories, again on a scale of 1-5 from the least feasible and most demanding from a technical perspective to the most feasible and easy to be implemented.

After these two iterations of voting, the final priority value for each user story derived, from the multiplication of the average values of the three dimensions (i.e. value, urgency and technical feasibility) for each user story.

The following section presents the application of the above-mentioned process, resulting in a final user stories' ranking and eventually the list of the BigDataOcean user stories that will be part of the first MVP release, as well as an outlining of the following releases plan.

4.2 MVP Definition

As described in the beginning of this chapter, a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) is all about validating the more crucial hypotheses of a product, which if they fail the whole idea is not functional any more. Two rounds of users' stories' voting had to be accomplished, from a business and from a technical perspective respectively, and in order to accommodate this need two google forms were created, where all partners came up to vote.

Figures

provide some screenshots that give a clearer picture of the process that was followed through the use of the google forms.

Figure 4.2 Landing pages for the 1st and 2nd round of voting on the user stories

Figure 4.3 Indicative example of voting by a partner

Figure 4.4 Thank you message for the voters

Figure 4.5 Part of the summary of results for the 1st round of user stories voting

In ANNEX II, the average scores for the three attributes of value, urgency and technical feasibility that came up from the partners' voting on the user stories as well as the computations that were made to extract their prioritisation can be found.

Along the following lines, Table 4-2 demonstrates the ranking of the user stories that emerged from the two iterations of voting. Furthermore, a mapping of the role defined by each user story to one of the four identified stakeholder groups in section 3.1 is implemented in the "Stakeholder group" column, in order to link them with the high-level envisioned actors of the BigDataOcean platform.

In certain cases, more than one of the four stakeholder groups of section 3.1 (i.e. Consumer, Data Provider, Service Provider and Curator) may apply to a given user story.

Table 4-2 Priority scores for the User Stories & Implied Features

Priority	ID	User Story	Score	Stakeholder group
1	US-3	As a data consumer, I want to be able to search for specific datasets, based on various criteria, or browse through a list of existing ones, so that I could easily and efficiently find relevant data to use.	77.5	Consumer
2	US-19	As a data analyst, I would like to have visualisation services, so that I can visually analyse existing datasets.	68.37	Consumer
3	US-9	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to create specific queries, so that I could obtain more relevant answers to reflect my requirements.	55.5	Consumer
4	US-4	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to explore the main properties of the available datasets or browse through a list of existing ones, so that I could easily find relevant data for my requirements.	54.83	Consumer
5	US-8	As a data consumer, I would like to use online tools for monitoring or reporting, so that I can generate relevant reports.	54.5	Consumer
6	US-26	As a manager, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data availability, so that data is available for data consumers at a required level of performance during normal or extraordinary operation.	50.48	Data provider
7	US-25	As a user, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data persistence so that I can be confident that my own data, and the data used by my processes/services, is always available and it will be for long time in the future.	50	Data provider/Consumer/Service provider
8	US-2	As an administrator, I want to be able to create an account to save my searches and preferences in the system, so that I could save my work for later reuse and manage its privacy levels.	47.5	ALL

9	US-29	As a data analyst, I want to find and use credible weather historical data, so that I can correlate them with my company's events' registry and come up with possible insights and/or patterns.	46.9	Consumer
10	US-28	As a data consumer, I want to find and use vessels' positioning information data, so that I can visualise them on a map for an easily digestible overview.	44.42	Consumer
11	US-22	As a data manager, I would like to download the generated reports produced by the system, so that I can self-archive them.	43.2	Data provider/Consumer
12	US-27	As a data consumer, I want the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data consistency, so that data storage is always conducted according to specific rules, and it is therefore easier to consume the required data.	42.4	Consumer
13	US-17	As a data manager, I would like to be able to manage the datasets to be represented using existing standards, so that it would be easier to consume them in the consequent stages of the data life cycle.	42.35	Data provider/Consumer
14	US-20	As a data consumer, I would like to receive recommendations about datasets, so that the BigDataOcean platform effectively helps me fulfil my information requirements.	41.07	Consumer
15	US-16	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to use datasets with heterogeneous formats, so that I would not be limited to only consume datasets of only a specific format.	40.7	Consumer
16	US-30	As a service consumer, I want to find and consume the "vessels' certified path" service, so that I can check whether a location for installing offshore equipment is safe.	40.4	Consumer
17	US-23	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to download the generated results of my queries or my services, so that I can store or further process them.	40.3	Consumer
18	US-7	As a data analyst, I would need analytics tools and services that can run on one or multiple datasets, so that I would be able to identify any abnormalities and also extract new knowledge.	39.6	Consumer

19	US-14	As a data manager, I would like to be able explore the service requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that availability and management of services can be better planned.	38.93	Service provider
20	US-24	As a data analyst, I would like to be able to create my own dashboards that will visualise existing data, so that I can analyse and compare different data sources.	38.68	Consumer
21	US-15	As a data manager, I would like to be able explore the data transformation requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that data transformation and curation of available datasets can be better planned.	38.5	Curator/Data provider
22	US-6	As a data consumer, I would like to view different quality metrics of the datasets, so that I can select the most appropriate data to use for my use case.	38.13	Consumer
23	US-13	As a data manager, I would like to be able explore the dataset requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that availability, storage, and management of datasets can be better planned.	36.8	Data provider
24	US-18	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to transform datasets, so that they can be used independently of their original format.	35.2	Consumer
25	US-11	As a service consumer, I would like to be able to configure and personalise existing services offered by the platform. This should be possible with an easy-to-use web interface that allows setting and tuning of variables and parameters of different services in order to better fit my requirements for data consumption.	34.2	Consumer
26	US-12	As a data provider, I would like to be able to describe and register specific datasets, so that I could make available metadata about datasets even if they are not integrated in the platform.	33.2	Data provider
27	US-5	As a data consumer, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to make available free downloading and purchasing of available datasets, so that diverse types of dataset access can be offered by the BigDataOcean platform.	29.6	Consumer
28	US-21	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to affect the results of services depending on varying priorities, so that the results reflect my needs better.	27.83	Consumer

29	US-1	As a data analyst, I want the BigDataOcean platform to have semantic services that allow to access correlated data, so that potentially new insights can be discovered.	25.8	Consumer
30	US-10	As a service developer, I would like to be able to build my own services through an easy-to-use web interface that allows for mashups and configurations of existing reusable services.	21.7	Service provider

Collecting User Stories that have an overall score from 77.5 to 41, i.e. the first 14th user stories (see Table 4-1), the critical initial implementation can be defined.

User stories that score under 41 are considered as valuable but not essential in the first round. These stories will be added in later iterations, as section 4.5 declares, and lead to a more refined implementation of the BigDataOcean methodology.

Grouping together the user stories per stakeholder group, various requirements are being shaped for each stakeholder (see Table 4-3Table 4-4Table 4-5Table 4-6).

Table 4-3 User Stories for the Consumer (Light green highlight for the MVP)

Consumer		
Priority	ID	User Story
1	US-3	As a data consumer, I want to be able to search for specific datasets, based on various criteria, or browse through a list of existing ones, so that I could easily and efficiently find relevant data to use.
2	US-19	As a data analyst, I would like to have visualisation services, so that I can visually analyse existing datasets.
3	US-9	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to create specific queries, so that I could obtain more relevant answers to reflect my requirements.
4	US-4	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to explore the main properties of the available datasets or browse through a list of existing ones, so that I could easily find relevant data for my requirements.
5	US-8	As a data consumer, I would like to use online tools for monitoring or reporting, so that I can generate relevant reports.
7	US-25	As a user, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data persistence so that I can be confident that my own data, and the data used by my processes/services, is always available and it will be for long time in the future.
8	US-2	As an administrator, I want to be able to create an account to save my searches and preferences in the system, so that I could save my work for later reuse and manage its privacy levels.
9	US-29	As a data analyst, I want to find and use credible weather historical data, so that I can correlate them with my company's events' registry and come up with possible insights and/or patterns.

10	US-28	As a data consumer, I want to find and use vessels' positioning information data, so that I can visualise them on a map for an easily digestible overview.
11	US-22	As a data manager, I would like to download the generated reports produced by the system, so that I can self-archive them.
12	US-27	As a data consumer, I want the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data consistency, so that data storage is always conducted according to specific rules, and it is therefore easier to consume the required data.
13	US-17	As a data manager, I would like to be able to manage the datasets to be represented using existing standards, so that it would be easier to consume them in the consequent stages of the data life cycle.
14	US-20	As a data consumer, I would like to receive recommendations about datasets, so that the BigDataOcean platform effectively helps me fulfil my information requirements.
15	US-16	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to use datasets with heterogeneous formats, so that I would not be limited to only consume datasets of only a specific format.
16	US-30	As a service consumer, I want to find and consume the "vessels' certified path" service, so that I can check whether a location for installing offshore equipment is safe.
17	US-23	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to download the generated results of my queries or my services, so that I can store or further process them.
18	US-7	As a data analyst, I would need analytics tools and services that can run on one or multiple datasets, so that I would be able to identify any abnormalities and also extract new knowledge.
20	US-24	As a data analyst, I would like to be able to create my own dashboards that will visualise existing data, so that I can analyse and compare different data sources.
22	US-6	As a data consumer, I would like to view different quality metrics of the datasets, so that I can select the most appropriate data to use for my use case.
24	US-18	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to transform datasets, so that they can be used independently of their original format.
25	US-11	As a service consumer, I would like to be able to configure and personalise existing services offered by the platform. This should be possible with an easy-to-use web interface that allows setting and tuning of variables and parameters of different services in order to better fit my requirements for data consumption.
27	US-5	As a data consumer, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to make available free downloading and purchasing of available datasets, so that diverse types of dataset access can be offered by the BigDataOcean platform.
28	US-21	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to affect the results of services depending on varying priorities, so that the results reflect my needs better.
29	US-1	As a data analyst, I want the BigDataOcean platform to have semantic services that allow to access correlated data, so that potentially new insights can be discovered.

Table 4-4 User Stories for the Data Provider (Light green highlight for the MVP)

Data provider		
Priority	ID	User Story
6	US-26	As a manager, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data availability, so that data is available for data consumers at a required level of performance during normal or extraordinary operation.
7	US-25	As a user, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data persistence so that I can be confident that my own data, and the data used by my processes/services, is always available and it will be for long time in the future.
11	US-22	As a data manager, I would like to download the generated reports produced by the system, so that I can self-archive them.
13	US-17	As a data manager, I would like to be able to manage the datasets to be represented using existing standards, so that it would be easier to consume them in the consequent stages of the data life cycle.
21	US-15	As a data manager, I would like to be able explore the data transformation requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that data transformation and curation of available datasets can be better planned.
23	US-13	As a data manager, I would like to be able explore the dataset requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that availability, storage, and management of datasets can be better planned.
26	US-12	As a data provider, I would like to be able to describe and register specific datasets, so that I could make available metadata about datasets even if they are not integrated in the platform.

Table 4-5 User Stories for the Service Provider (Light green highlight for the MVP)

Service provider		
Priority	ID	User Story
7	US-25	As a user, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data persistence so that I can be confident that my own data, and the data used by my processes/services, is always available and it will be for long time in the future.
8	US-2	As an administrator, I want to be able to create an account to save my searches and preferences in the system, so that I could save my work for later reuse and manage its privacy levels.
19	US-14	As a data manager, I would like to be able explore the service requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that availability and management of services can be better planned.
30	US-10	As a service developer, I would like to be able to build my own services through an easy-to-use web interface that allows for mashups and configurations of existing reusable services.

Table 4-6 User Stories for the Curator (Light green highlight for the MVP)

Curator		
Priority	ID	User Story
8	US-2	As an administrator, I want to be able to create an account to save my searches and preferences in the system, so that I could save my work for later reuse and manage its privacy levels.
21	US-15	As a data manager, I would like to be able explore the data transformation requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that data transformation and curation of available datasets can be better planned.

It can be observed that most user stories as well as the highest rated ones refer to the role of the Consumer, a conclusion that is anticipated from the definition of the MVP as the Minimum Viable Product to collect the maximum amount of validated learning about customers with the least effort.

4.3 Workflows

Voted user stories for the Consumer's case have been abstracted to a sequence of steps, each of which is related to a number of implied features in order for the described functionality to be provided by the BigDataOcean platform and tools. For the three other stakeholders' roles, the number of the voted user stories does not allow to come up with integrated, meaningful workflows for the MVP.

Figure 4.6 Customer's workflow diagram for the MVP

The workflow diagram that is being shaped for the consumer's role in the platform builds upon the voted for the MVP user stories and prescribes certain steps for the platform's consumer that delineate

implied features/components that the platform should have, from a more high-level, business perspective.

The user stories, however, defined in D4.1, present different levels of abstraction, with some of them being more specific, whereas other refer to more technical characteristics that the platform should have that cannot be represented in a workflow diagram, coming, also, in alignment with section 3.2, the Back-office Methodology. In that view, user stories such as US-17, US-25 & US-27, which are part of the MVP, should be given specific attention for the back-office methodological features that the platform should have, dealing with issues such as data harmonisation, data interoperability, data storage, etc.

4.4 Discussion/ Comparative Analysis between MVP Workflows and Methodology Workflows

It can be noticed that the voted user stories for the MVP as seen in the corresponding tables (Table 4-3Table 4-4Table 4-5Table 4-6) as well as the workflow diagram for the consumer (Figure 4.6) are in direct alignment with the methodology proposed in section 3, both the front-office and the back-office methodology.

To further clarify this argument, the following table maps each user story with either a step of the front-office methodology (section 3.1) or a technical challenge identified and handled by the BigDataOcean Back-office methodology (section 3.2).

Table 4-7 Mapping of the user stories with the methodology

Pr.	ID	User Story	Front-Office Methodology	Back-office Methodology
1	US-3	As a data consumer, I want to be able to search for specific datasets, based on various criteria, or browse through a list of existing ones, so that I could easily and efficiently find relevant data to use.	Search/Browse Datasets/Services	-
2	US-19	As a data analyst, I would like to have visualisation services, so that I can visually analyse existing datasets.	View/ Query/Process Data & Services (Build Queries & Visualisations)	-
3	US-9	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to create specific queries, so that I could obtain more relevant answers to reflect my requirements.	View/ Query/Process Data & Services (Build Queries & Visualisations)	-
4	US-4	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to explore the main properties of the available datasets or browse through a list of existing ones, so that I could easily find relevant data for my requirements.	View Resource Preview	-

5	US-8	As a data consumer, I would like to use online tools for monitoring or reporting, so that I can generate relevant reports.	View/ Query/Process Data & Services (Create Report)	-
6	US-26	As a manager, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data availability, so that data is available for data consumers at a required level of performance during normal or extraordinary operation.	Make data available	-
7	US-25	As a user, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data persistence so that I can be confident that my own data, and the data used by my processes/services, is always available and it will be for long time in the future.	-	Data check-in
8	US-2	As an administrator, I want to be able to create an account to save my searches and preferences in the system, so that I could save my work for later reuse and manage its privacy levels.	Get access	-
9	US-29	As a data analyst, I want to find and use credible weather historical data, so that I can correlate them with my company's events' registry and come up with possible insights and/or patterns.	Search/Browse Datasets/Services	Interactive Service Building / Service Offering
10	US-28	As a data consumer, I want to find and use vessels' positioning information data, so that I can visualise them on a map for an easily digestible overview.	Search/Browse Datasets/Services/ Build Queries and Visualisations	Service offering
11	US-22	As a data manager, I would like to download the generated reports produced by the system, so that I can self-archive them.	View/Query Process Data & Services	-
12	US-27	As a data consumer, I want the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data consistency, so that data storage is always conducted according to specific rules, and it is therefore easier to consume the required data.	-	Curation
13	US-17	As a data manager, I would like to be able to manage the datasets to be represented using existing standards, so that it would be easier to consume them in the consequent stages of the data life cycle.	-	Curation
14	US-20	As a data consumer, I would like to receive recommendations about datasets, so that the BigDataOcean platform effectively helps me fulfil my information requirements.	-	Dataset Recommendation

15	US-16	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to use datasets with heterogeneous formats, so that I would not be limited to only consume datasets of only a specific format.	-	Interactive Service Building
16	US-30	As a service consumer, I want to find and consume the “vessels’ certified path” service, so that I can check whether a location for installing offshore equipment is safe.	Search/Browse Datasets/Services & View/Query/Process Data & Services	-
17	US-23	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to download the generated results of my queries or my services, so that I can store or further process them.	View/Query Process Data & Services	-
18	US-7	As a data analyst, I would need analytics tools and services that can run on one or multiple datasets, so that I would be able to identify any abnormalities and also extract new knowledge.	View/Query Process Data & Services (Explore & Monitor Analytics)	Interactive Service Building
19	US-14	As a data manager, I would like to be able to explore the service requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that availability and management of services can be better planned.	View Requests	-
20	US-24	As a data analyst, I would like to be able to create my own dashboards that will visualise existing data, so that I can analyse and compare different data sources.	View/Query/Process Data & Services (Build Queries & Visualisations)	Interactive Service Building
21	US-15	As a data manager, I would like to be able to explore the data transformation requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that data transformation and curation of available datasets can be better planned.	View Curation Needs/ Requests & View Requests	-
22	US-6	As a data consumer, I would like to view different quality metrics of the datasets, so that I can select the most appropriate data to use for my use case.	View Resource Preview (Advanced Insights)	-
23	US-13	As a data manager, I would like to be able to explore the dataset requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that availability, storage, and management of datasets can be better planned.	View Requests	-
24	US-18	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to transform datasets, so that they can be used independently of their original format.	View/Query/Process Data & Services	Interactive Service Building

25	US-11	As a service consumer, I would like to be able to configure and personalise existing services offered by the platform. This should be possible with an easy-to-use web interface that allows setting and tuning of variables and parameters of different services in order to better fit my requirements for data consumption.	View/Query/Process Data & Services	Interactive Service Building
26	US-12	As a data provider, I would like to be able to describe and register specific datasets, so that I could make available metadata about datasets even if they are not integrated in the platform.	Improve Data	Big Data Annotation
27	US-5	As a data consumer, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to make available free downloading and purchasing of available datasets, so that diverse types of dataset access can be offered by the BigDataOcean platform.	Get Access	-
28	US-21	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to affect the results of services depending on varying priorities, so that the results reflect my needs better.	View/Query Process Data & Services (Explore & Monitor Analytics)	Interactive Service Building
29	US-1	As a data analyst, I want the BigDataOcean platform to have semantic services that allow to access correlated data, so that potentially new insights can be discovered.	-	Semantic Annotation
30	US-10	As a service developer, I would like to be able to build my own services through an easy-to-use web interface that allows for mashups and configurations of existing reusable services.	Create Service & Update/Readjust Service	Interactive Service Building

As it can be seen, functionalities such as searching and browsing for data, building queries and visualisations, creating reports and having access to a “smart” preview for the available datasets seem to be on top of priorities for the pilot partners while it is also considered something of both value, urgency and technical feasibility by the technical partners. On top of these functionalities, certain requirements are also being outlined through the voted user stories, dealing with platform’s technical (back-office) characteristics that its stakeholders are considering as indispensable. These user stories can be directly mapped with the identified back-office technical challenges under section 3.2, as the last column of Table 4-7 indicates. In that view, US-25, for example, will be handled under “Data check-in”, while US-29 calls for “interactive service building” and “service offering”, two technical challenges also recognised and methodologically prescribed in sections 3.2.3 and 3.2.2 of the present deliverable respectively. The alignment with the methodology is also confirmed for the user stories, not voted to be part of the MVP but considered as valuable for the next releases, where features such as exploration of analytics or view requests and view curation needs are being introduced.

Furthermore, in the context of deliverable D2.1 a study on project requirements was realised, mainly based on the needs of the pilots (end-users), resulting on a set of 62 raw requirements for the BigDataOcean solution. With the identification of these requirements, the Elicitation phase (as described in D2.1) ends. The deliverable at hand initiates the Analysis phase, by prioritising the User Stories in order to support the definition of the BigDataOcean MVP.

Each of the BigDataOcean raw requirements was mapped to one of the five different steps in the BigDataOcean Value Chain (namely "Data Acquisition", "Data Pre-Processing", "Data Curation", "Data Storage" and "Data Usage"). As a next step, the requirements were also mapped to the user stories described in the context of D4.1; the same user stories that constitute the main input for defining the BigDataOcean MVP. Three different types of mappings came up: i) Direct map between a single requirement and a user story; ii) Mapping several requirements to a user story; iii) Indirect map between a requirement and a user story (in this case a requirement is treated as a necessity for the requirement). Through this process, the consortium ensured that the raw requirements reported in the context of D2.1 are properly taken into consideration and reflected in the BigDataOcean MVP.

4.5 Releases plan

Four releases of the BigDataOcean Web Platform have been prescribed even from the DOA, for months 14th, 18th, 24th and 30th of the project's duration. Based on the MVP voted user stories, it is now possible to create an initial plan about what each release is expected to deliver from the list of user stories, while taking into consideration the derived prioritisation.

It needs to be stressed that MVP is a product and for that purposes it is not feasible to be considered for the first release that is planned for M14. At this first release the BigDataOcean platform's mockups are expected to derive as well as an initial working prototype.

In contrast with a Scrum approach that declares that an MVP should be defined at the end of the project, lean approach considers a real MVP in almost every release. Towards this end and following a lean methodology, MVP is expected to be delivered in the 2nd release (1-14th voted user story), i.e. M18 under D5.4, while the following release on M24 according to the release plan agreed by the consortium will deliver 15th-25th User Stories from the derived prioritised list. Final five user stories are planned for the Final Release of the platform that is planned for M30.

However, it should be taken into account that the aforementioned planning is an initial one, while alterations and additions may arise in D4.3 (M15) for the user stories and in D2.3 (M18) for their prioritisation.

Figure 4.7 BigDataOcean Releases Plan

5 Conclusions and Next Steps

5.1 Key take-aways

The present deliverable documents the results of T2.4 “BigDataOcean Methodology Elaboration and BigDataOcean MVP Definition” that ran from M1 until M6 of the project, and had two main goals, as the title of the task indicates; to define the BigDataOcean Methodology and to describe the MVP (Minimum Viable Product) that will guide the next implementation steps of the project, while ensuring market viability.

For that purpose, it was decided that a collaborative approach should be undertaken for the phases of the task, since this deliverable will set the basis for all next steps of the project and it is of utmost importance for all partners to be engaged and aligned on which is the goal of the project and what is going to be implemented.

Towards this end, it was decided that fast prototyping sessions should run to test both technical challenges that BigDataOcean should confront, where all BigDataOcean partners were engaged, and the usefulness of the solution from a business perspective, where the pilot partners were invited to validate the results to ensure that the solution to be described should accommodate the needs of the stakeholders of the four BigDataOcean pilot cases.

The results of the fast prototyping sessions paved the way for the BigDataOcean Methodology, which was decided to be separated in two parts: the Front-office Methodology and the Back-office Methodology, in order to facilitate the consortium in reaching a common understanding on the solution’s offerings through the first, while leaving for the latter the ways to solve the technical challenges that emerge from the workflows described in the front-office methodology.

Finally, after the delivery of the User Stories on M5 in D4.1, the process to define the MVP could start, since it was decided that it will come out from the User stories, through a synergetic, democratic approach among all partners of the consortium, who voted on the User stories to evaluate according to their view their value and their urgency. A second round of voting among the technical partners to evaluate the feasibility of the voted user stories, ensured that the selected for the MVP user stories, does not only demonstrate a high value and necessity, but they are also doable in the available timeframe. The 14 top voted user stories were selected to represent the MVP for BigDataOcean and guide the technical developments of the project. High affinity was observed among the MVP and the methodological workflows described in chapter 3, a fact that validates that the methodology proposed is aligned with all partners’ perception and vision for BigDataOcean and ensures closeness with the market’s needs, as these are represented by the pilot partners of the consortium (i.e. ANEK, FOINIKAS, HCMR, NESTER, EXMILE).

5.2 Next steps

During the next months of the project updates on the desk research on Big Data components and tools (T2.1), possible updates on the information sources & needs identification analysis (T2.2) and updates on the value chain definition (T2.3) may emerge and will be documented as part of D2.3. These updates along with any potential updates on the user stories (D4.3, M15) will serve as input for T2.4 which may impose updates and amendments on both the methodology and the MVP that will be finalised on M18 and documented also in D2.3 “Final BigDataOcean Methodology”.

6 Annexes

6.1 Annex I –References

Knapp, J., Zeratsky, J. (Product designer), & Kowitz, B. (Product designer). (n.d.). *Sprint: how to solve big problems and test new ideas in just five days*.

Ries, E. (2011). *The Lean Startup. How Today's Entrepreneurs Use Continuous Innovation to Create Radically Successful Businesses*. <https://doi.org/23>

6.2 Annex II – Aggregated Results of the User Stories Voting

ID	User Story	Value	Urgency	Technical Feasibility	Priority Score
		Average Scores			Priority Score
US-1	As a data analyst, I want the BigDataOcean platform to have semantic services that allow to access correlated data, so that potentially new insights can be discovered.	3.67	3.07	2.25	25.30
US-2	As an administrator, I want to be able to create an account to save my searches and preferences in the system, so that I could save my work for later reuse and manage its privacy levels.	4.00	3.07	3.75	46.00
US-3	As a data consumer, I want to be able to search for specific datasets, based on various criteria, or browse through a list of existing ones, so that I could easily and efficiently find relevant data to use.	4.60	4.47	3.75	77.05
US-4	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to explore the main properties of the available datasets or browse through a list of existing ones, so that I could easily find relevant data for my requirements.	4.07	3.73	3.5	53.14
US-5	As a data consumer, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to make available free downloading and purchasing of available datasets, so that diverse types of dataset access can be offered by the BigDataOcean platform.	3.47	2.67	3	27.73
US-6	As a data consumer, I would like to view different quality metrics of the datasets, so that I can select the most appropriate data to use for my use case.	3.47	3.20	3.25	36.05
US-7	As a data analyst, I would need analytics tools and services that can run on one or multiple datasets, so that I would be able to identify any abnormalities and also extract new knowledge.	4.00	3.20	3	38.40
US-8	As a data consumer, I would like to use online tools for monitoring or reporting, so that I can generate relevant reports.	4.00	3.47	3.75	52.00

US-9	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to create specific queries, so that I could obtain more relevant answers to reflect my requirements.	4.07	3.53	3.75	53.88
US-10	As a service developer, I would like to be able to build my own services through an easy-to-use web interface that allows for mashups and configurations of existing reusable services.	3.93	3.07	1.75	21.11
US-11	As a service consumer, I would like to be able to configure and personalise existing services offered by the platform. This should be possible with an easy-to-use web interface that allows setting and tuning of variables and parameters of different services in order to better fit my requirements for data consumption.	3.67	3.00	3	33.00
US-12	As a data provider, I would like to be able to describe and register specific datasets, so that I could make available metadata about datasets even if they are not integrated in the platform.	3.53	2.93	3	31.09
US-13	As a data manager, I would like to be able to explore the dataset requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that availability, storage, and management of datasets can be better planned.	3.20	2.73	4	34.99
US-14	As a data manager, I would like to be able to explore the service requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that availability and management of services can be better planned.	3.33	2.80	4	37.33
US-15	As a data manager, I would like to be able to explore the data transformation requests that have been received through the BigDataOcean platform, so that data transformation and curation of available datasets can be better planned.	3.47	2.93	3.75	38.13
US-16	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to use datasets with heterogeneous formats, so that I would not be limited to only consume datasets of only a specific format.	4.20	3.47	2.75	40.04
US-17	As a data manager, I would like to be able to manage the datasets to be represented using existing standards, so that it would be easier to consume them in the consequent stages of the data life cycle.	4.20	3.60	2.75	41.58
US-18	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to transform datasets, so that they can be used independently of their original format.	3.80	3.20	2.75	33.44
US-19	As a data analyst, I would like to have visualisation services, so that I can visually analyse existing datasets.	4.53	4.27	3.5	67.70

US-20	As a data consumer, I would like to receive recommendations about datasets, so that the BigDataOcean platform effectively helps me fulfil my information requirements.	3.73	3.00	3.5	39.20
US-21	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to affect the results of services depending on varying priorities, so that the results reflect my needs better.	3.40	3.13	2.5	26.63
US-22	As a data manager, I would like to download the generated reports produced by the system, so that I can self-archive them.	3.67	2.80	4	41.07
US-23	As a data consumer, I would like to be able to download the generated results of my queries or my services, so that I can store or further process them.	3.73	3.13	3.25	38.02
US-24	As a data analyst, I would like to be able to create my own dashboards that will visualise existing data, so that I can analyse and compare different data sources.	4.07	3.40	2.75	38.02
US-25	As a user, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data persistence so that I can be confident that my own data, and the data used by my processes/services, is always available and it will be for long time in the future.	4.40	3.73	3	49.28
US-26	As a manager, I would like the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data availability, so that data is available for data consumers at a required level of performance during normal or extraordinary operation.	4.13	3.67	3.25	49.26
US-27	As a data consumer, I want the BigDataOcean platform to ensure data consistency, so that data storage is always conducted according to specific rules, and it is therefore easier to consume the required data.	4.00	3.47	3	41.60
US-28	As a data consumer, I want to find and use vessels' positioning information data, so that I can visualise them on a map for an easily digestible overview.	3.87	3.40	3.25	42.73
US-29	As a data analyst, I want to find and use credible weather historical data, so that I can correlate them with my company's events' registry and come up with possible insights and/or patterns.	3.87	3.40	3.5	46.01
US-30	As a service consumer, I want to find and consume the "vessels' certified path" service, so that I can check whether a location for installing offshore equipment is safe.	3.80	3.47	3	39.52